

**LONG-TERM VARIATIONS IN THE
GLACIERS OF THE ALAKNANDA
BASIN (CENTRAL HIMALAYA)
USING SPACE AND GROUND-BASED
OBSERVATIONS**

By

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List of Acronyms

AAR	Area Altitude Ratio
AKB	Alaknanda Basin
BKG	Bhagirath Kharak Glacier
BG	Bagnyu Glacier
CGWB	Central Ground Water Board
CRU TS	Climate Research Unit Time Series
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
DGPS	Differential Global Positioning System
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
ELA	Equilibrium Line Altitude
ERDAS	Earth Resources Data Analysis System
ESRI	Environmental Systems Research Institute
ETM	Enhanced Thematic Mapper
FCC	False Colour Composites
GCP	Ground Control Points
GPS	Global Positioning System
GSI	Geological Survey of India
HHC	Higher Himalayan Crystalline
HMA	High Mountain Asia
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IRS	Indian Remote sensing Satellite
LHCS	Lesser Himalayan crystalline sequence
LHM	Lesser Himalaya Metasedimentaries
LIA	Little Ice Age

LPS	Leica Photogrammetry Suite
MB	Mass Balance
MCT	Main Central Thrust
NDSI	Normalize Difference Snow Index
OLI	Operational Land Imager
OSL	Optically stimulated Luminescence
PPK	Point-to-Point Kinematic
RGI	Randolph Glacier Inventory
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
SDC	Supraglacial Debris Cover
SOI	Survey of India
SPG	Satopanth Glacier
SRTM	Shuttle Radar Topography Mission
STDS	South Tibetan Detachment System
SWIR	Short Wave Infrared
TBG	Tipra Bank Glacier
TSS	Tethyan Sedimentary Sequence
USGS	United States Geological Survey
WGMS	World Glacier Monitoring Service

Abstract

The Himalaya is the largest abode of glaciers outside the Polar regions. These glaciers contribute to a significant portion of the freshwater flowing in some of the major river systems in the world, like the Indus, the Ganga, and the Brahmaputra. Water from these rivers is a source of fresh water for domestic use, irrigation, hydropower, fishery, inland navigation, and other requirements for more than 1.3 billion people living downstream. Hence, the Himalaya is also termed as a ‘water tower’ and ‘third pole’ of the globe. However, climate warming in the recent decades has brought about a drastic change in glaciers the world over, including the Himalayan glaciers. Hence, glacier retreat and mass loss in the Himalaya have become major concerns among scientists and policymakers.

The present research work is the most comprehensive study on the glaciers of the Alaknanda Basin, Central Himalaya. One of the primary objectives of this study is to create an inventory of the glaciers in the Alaknanda Basin using historical and recent satellite data (Chapter 2). The data set used are mainly the Corona images of 1968 for the identification of glaciers in the historical period and Sentinel-2A images of 2020 for the recent period. The glacier boundaries delineated from the older and contemporary periods act as the basis for analysing changes in the length and area of glaciers in the basin from 1968 to 2020. The change in length of glaciers measured along the central flow line of each glacier provide estimates for the recession of glaciers. The results suggest that the annual average recession of glaciers in the basin is 11.75 ± 1.6 m/year for the corresponding period. The glaciated area of the basin has reduced to 683 ± 47.81 km² from 742 ± 44.4 km², while the number of glaciers increased to 116 from 98, between 1968 – 2020. The debris cover of the glaciers in the basin has also increased by ~38% from 2000 to 2020. Besides, the climatic data analysis reveals an increase in winter-time temperature (0.03 °C/year) between 1968–2020 in the basin. Furthermore, the analysis of topographical parameters of the glaciers reveals that the small glaciers (< 5 km²) with lower altitude snout and higher slope have registered more significant area loss and higher retreat rate. Hence, smaller glaciers are observed to be more sensitive to climate change, because of their short response times, and can therefore serve as good indicators of changes in climatic conditions. The glacier expedition conducted in September 2019 was

useful to verify some of the results obtained in this study. In addition, this study provides a detailed database of glaciers in the basin, which includes important information on glacier recession, altitude, slope, aspect, and fragmenting glaciers in the basin.

Glacier mass loss has a cascading effect on the heavily populated downstream regions of the rivers originating from the Himalayan glaciers. The present study computes (Chapter 3) the mass budget of 61 glaciers in the Alaknanda Basin from 2000 to 2017, using a satellite-based geodetic technique. The utilization of Cartosat-1 stereo pairs to make a high-resolution Digital Elevation Model (DEM) for the basin is one of the highlights of the study. The Cartosat-1 DEM for 2011, 2014, and 2017 are subtracted from the global SRTM DEM of 2000, to estimate time variations of elevation change and glacier mass budget. The results suggest a sustained mass loss of 1.85 ± 0.10 Gt out of 33.9 ± 8.8 Gt for 61 glaciers in the basin from 2000-2017. The mass budget of all the glaciers is tending towards negative values. The accuracy of the computed DEMs is improved by utilizing Differential Global Positioning System (DGPS) data available in the two benchmark glaciers Satopanth Glacier (SPG) and Bhagirath Karakh Glacier (BKG) in the basin. Significant mass loss is also estimated for both the SPG (-0.57 ± 0.06 m w.e/a) and the BKG (-0.56 ± 0.06 m w.e/a) between the years 2000-2017, which may be influenced by the presence of extended debris cover and supraglacial lakes in the ablation zone of these glaciers. The results also compare well with an earlier estimate of the field-based glaciological mass budget for the SPG.

The third main objective of this research is to reconstruct the past extent of the major glaciers in the Alaknanda Basin, which are SPG, BKG, and the Bhagnyu Glacier (BG). The study has used maximum available data in the study area starting from the historic Survey of India toposheets (SOI) (1882, 1936, and 1956) to the recent Sentinel-1 data (2020) and verified with the field evidence collected during the glacier expedition conducted in 2019. High-resolution Google Earth imageries are also used to facilitate the comparison of our results. This part of the study mainly addresses the important aspects of past glacier history on a geospatial domain and is supplemented by field investigation. The glacier valleys and the associated geomorphological signatures helps to infer the extent of past glaciation in the region. The satellite image signatures and the strong field evidence indicate that the glaciers in the Alaknanda Basin experienced glacial advances up to Mana village, which is ~ 8.4 km from the present snout of the glacier. The terminus

of the trunk glacier in the past period is reconstructed from the erosional and depositional landforms identified in the glacial valleys. Different morainic deposits identified in the valley such as lateral, recessional & terminal moraines confirm the retreating trend of the glaciers.

The comprehensive analysis shows the glacier reduction in the Alaknanda Basin, in the form of retreat and volume loss. The increasing global temperatures are frequently viewed as the cause of glacial melt and it has been explicitly linked to regional climatic factors. In the Alaknanda Basin, between 1901 and 2020, there is an increasing trend in temperature ($0.01^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{year}$) with a concomitant decreasing trend in precipitation ($0.1\text{mm}/\text{year}$). The continuous melting of glaciers in the Alaknanda Basin affects the storage of ice volume. It can further lead to the shortage of freshwater availability on the glacier fed river system. The glacier loss in the Himalaya is affecting the freshwater flows with dramatic adverse effects on biodiversity, people, and livelihoods, with a possible long-term implication on regional food security. Overall, retreating glaciers over the next several decades are likely to affect the variability in the downstream areas and endanger the sustainability of water use in the holy basins of the Himalaya.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Glaciers

Glaciers are hard, thick, and compact ice masses on land that form through the recrystallization of snow and move forward under their weight (Dhobal 2011). In simple words, a glacier is formed by the continuous accumulation of snow and it becomes denser by the increasing weight of the overlying snowpack, subsequently converting the snow into ice (Paterson 1994). Glaciers move or flow downslope under the influence of their mass and gravity. Glaciers constitute a major source of fresh water on the earth and a significant contributor to sea-level changes.

A glacier is primarily compartmentalised into the accumulation zone and ablation zone. In the accumulation zone, the glacier builds up or accumulates mass, whereas in the ablation zone it shrinks or loses mass. The accumulation area of the glacier is at a higher altitude compared to the ablation zone. The glacier ice always moves from the accumulation region to the ablation region. The ending point of the glacier called the glacier terminus or glacier snout is usually at the lowest altitude. The accumulation process of a glacier includes the snow and ice accumulation from direct precipitation. Avalanche and wind blow also contribute to snow accumulation. The ablation process on the glacier includes surface melt, sublimation, calving, etc. The Equilibrium Line Altitude (ELA) is a zone that differentiates the accumulation from the ablation zone of a glacier. It is usually marked at the end of the ablation season, which is the end of September/October.

1.2 Glaciers on a Global Scenario

Glaciers occupy nearly ten percent of the total land area in the globe. They are the largest reservoir of fresh water on earth. Eighty percent of the Earth's freshwater is in the form of glaciers and glacier ice. Most of these glacial ices are located in Antarctica (~90%) and Greenland (8%), and the remaining are present in almost all the continents around the world except Australia(<https://www.usgs.gov/special-topics/water-science->

school/science/ice-snow-and-glaciers-and-water-cycle). Figure 1 represents the glaciated regions on the Earth.

Figure 1.1: Glaciated regions on the earth

(<https://naturalresources-freshwater.weebly.com/>)

Glaciers including the ice sheets and ice caps of Greenland and Antarctica cover an area of ~706,000 km² (RGI, 2017). The volume storage of these glaciers is 170,000 cubic kilometers and it contributes ~0.4 meters of potential sea-level-rise (Huss and Farinotti 2012; Zemp et al., 2020). The mountain glaciers and their imprints are the prominent evidence of glaciation two million years ago. These glaciers are retreating at an alarming rate since the 18th century (NSIDC.org).

The recording of glacier variations started in 1894, and the World Glacier Monitoring Service (WGMS) started maintaining records of glacier changes from 1986. WGMS contains the standardized observations on glacier inventories, mass and volume changes, area, and length measurements of glaciers, etc. Such a huge database is the key input in climate change observations. Besides these are the basic pieces of information about glaciers used in the glaciological application, glacial geomorphology, and quaternary sciences. These data can also be used as the primary data for hydrological modeling along with the possible effects of atmospheric warming.

In recent decades glaciers are melting rapidly all over the world mainly due to global warming and anthropogenic climate change. The estimates of glacier loss taken over the past century (Haeberli and Hoelzle, 2001; Zemp et al 2015; WGMS, 2020)

indicate, that mountain glaciers are shrinking on a global scale. The global glacier mass loss during the period 1851 to 2010 is $25 \pm 35\%$ and in 1991-2010 it has increased to $69 \pm 24\%$ (Marzeion et al., 2014). The satellite gravimetry and local glaciological observation during 2003–2009 conducted by Gardner et al., 2013 reported large glacier loss in the Arctic, Canada, Alaska, coastal Greenland, the southern Andes, and high-mountain Asia. A slightly lesser rate is observed in Antarctica. The total estimated global glacier loss is -259 ± 28 Gt per year. The regional runoff and sea-level rise are the noticeable feedback due to the glacier reduction, and indicators of climate change, especially in the recent decades (Huss and Hock 2018; Marzeion et al., 2014; Radić et al., 2014; Zemp et al., 2020). A large quantity of water (around 328 billion tons) has been transferred into the oceans every year in the last decade (Hugonnet et al., 2021). The global scale glacier mass balance study from 1961 to 2016 carried out by Zemp et al., 2019 reported that glacier loss in the Alaskan region is the largest contributor to sea-level rise (8 mm sea-level equivalent). The annual mass balance of glaciers by direct measurements since 1960 reports that the estimated value is less than zero, and the estimates are tending to show more negative values after 1970 (Kaser et al., 2006).

Increased availability of satellite imagery from remote sensing platforms with adequate spatial and temporal resolutions, near-global coverage, and relatively low financial obligations allow measurements of glacier parameters over larger areas for extended periods (Racoviteanu et al. 2008; Bolch et al. 2010; Burns and Nolin, 2014; Gardent et al., 2014). Monitoring glaciers using remote sensing data is the most common technique since the 1980s. Satellite data including both optical and radar images are extensively used to estimate the glacier length, area, mass balance change, estimating ELA, surface velocity, formation, and expansion of supraglacial lakes, especially on mountain glaciers globally. (Wessels et al., 2002; Khalsa et al., 2004; Berthier et al., 2007; Scherler et al., 2008; Mathieu et al., 2009). The Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) from the Terra and Aqua satellites have provided daily global snow cover products since 2000 (Hall et al., 2002; Wang et al., 2008). All this information has been widely applied in different fields, such as hydrology, agriculture, climatic related studies including snow and cryosphere studies (Wang & Xie, 2009; Wang et al., 2017). The Landsat era since the 1990s with moderate resolution images (30m), followed by higher resolution Advanced Spaceborne Thermal Emission and Reflection

Radiometer (ASTER) (15m), Sentinel-2 (10m) are used to update the glacier inventories such as Randolph Glacier Inventory (RGI), Global Land Ice Measurements from Space (GLIMS) and Glacier Area Mapping for Discharge from the Asian Mountains (GAMDAM), etc. (Pfeffer et al., 2014; Nuimura, et al., 2015). The high-resolution DEMs covering polar regions such as AeroDEM (Korsgaard et al., 2016), ArticDEM (Porter et al., 2018), and other globally available DEMs such as TanDEM-X (Wessel et al., 2016), Cloud and land Elevation Satellite (ICESat), Shuttle Radar Topographic Mission (SRTM), Advanced ASTER, are used to monitor large scale glacier elevation change, mass balance and volume changes (Wang et al., 2017; Albedyll et al. 2018; Huber et al 2020). The glacier velocity estimates on a global scale are available from the optical as well as the Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) data (Dehecq et al., 2015; Rosenau et al., 2015; Kääb et al., 2016; Vincent et al., 2016; King et al, 2018; Millan et al., 2019; Pronk et al., 2021; Samsonov et al., 2021). Many of the glacier inventories, recession estimates, ice dynamics, and mass balance studies have improved through satellite data analyses, and many models are now available that give a realistic picture of the glacier status worldwide (Berthier *et al.*, 2007; Heid and Kaab, 2012; Kargel *et al.*, 2005; Bolch *et al.*, 2011, 2008; Quincey and Glasser, 2009; Scherler *et al.*, 2011; Benn *et al.*, 2003; Benn *et al.*, 2012; Paul and Andreassen, 2009; Paul and Kääb, 2005; Paul et al., 2007; Oerlamans, 2000; Grinsted 2013; Pfeffer et al., 2014; Rowan et al., 2015; Brun et al ., 2017; Zhou et al., 2018; Zemp et al., 2019; Immerzeel et al., 2020; King et al., 2020; Shean et al., 2020; Bolibar et al 2022).

Global retreat and mass loss of mountain glaciers are likely to continue throughout the 21st century (Gardner et al., 2013; Marzeion et al., 2012; Radić et al., 2014; Huss and Hock, 2015). According to the climate change scenarios (RCP 8.5) by Shannon et al. 2019, the average loss in glacier volume is predicted to be $-64 \pm 5\%$, by the end of the century. Some of the regions like Central Europe, Caucasus, High Mountain Asia, and Southern Andes will experience mass losses of around 75%. The warming rates will be even higher, in the higher altitude regions of the Himalaya compared to the lower plain regions. (Vuille et al., 2008; Pepin et al., 2015; Kraaijenbrink et al., 2017).

The historical terminus positions for selected glaciers are generally reconstructed from the topographical maps, photos, satellite images, dating the moraine samples, and some other sources (Lopez et al., 2010; Nussbaumer et al., 2011; Davies and Glasser,

2012; Leclercq and Oerlemans, 2012; Rabatel et al., 2013). The reconstructed extent of selected glaciers exist for 3000 years (Holzhauser et al., 2005). A larger number of glaciation records from the 16th and 17th centuries are available by Zemp et al., 2011. The glacier length reconstruction records on a global scale are used to identify the sea level rise contribution (Leclercq et al., 2011) and also temperature reconstruction on a hemispheric scale.

1.3 Glaciers in High Mountain Asia (HMA)

The HMA consists of a series of mountain ranges i.e., the Himalaya, the Pamirs, the Tien Shan, and the Tibetan Plateau. There are more than 80,000 glaciers present in this region. The downstream population is highly dependent on the rivers which originate from the glaciers in the HMA for various purposes such as drinking water, agriculture, irrigation, hydro-power generations, and many more. A slight increase in the runoff due to excessive glacier melt is reflected by the increased water levels in these rivers (Bhattacharya et al., 2021).

The mass balance estimates from geodetic methods suggest that most glaciers in HMA are losing mass over the past two decades (Brun et al., 2017; Shean et al., 2020; Zemp et al., 2019; Bhattacharya et al., 2021). Observations by Bhattacharya et al., (2021) reveal high loss in glacial mass in Northern Tien Shan ($-0.60 \pm 0.07\% \text{ a}^{-1}$) and Western Nyainqentanglha ($-0.30 \pm 0.02\% \text{ a}^{-1}$) compared to the other regions in HMA. The regional mass balance observation is $-0.40 \pm 0.07 \text{ m w.e. a}^{-1}$ in Central and Northern Tien Shan and $-0.06 \pm 0.07 \text{ m w.e. a}^{-1}$ in Eastern Pamir regions. These are the highest mass loss values reported in the Central Himalaya and Northern Tien Shan after 2015 (Bhattacharya et al., 2021). The mass balance estimates of glaciers in HMA by Shean et al., 2020 and Brun et al., 2017 is in the range of $-0.19 \pm 0.03 \text{ m w.e. yr}^{-1}$ (2000-2018) and $-0.18 \pm 0.04 \text{ m w.e. yr}^{-1}$ (2000-2016) respectively. However, the in-situ measurements are available only for 30 out of 80,000 glaciers in HMA and only two glaciers have mass balance estimates for more than 30 years (Bolch et al., 2019; Bhattacharya et al., 2021).

Himalaya is the youngest mountain range in the world. The length of this mountain range is ~2400 km and the width is ~300-320 km. Himalaya consists of more than 20,000 glaciers with an ice storage range of 2955 and 4737 km³ (Frey et al., 2012). The estimated

glacial area of the Himalayan and Karakoram Ranges is ~ 40,800 km² (Bolch et al., 2012). The Indian Himalayan region is divided into Western Himalaya (Himachal and Kashmir), Central Himalaya (Uttarakhand), and Eastern Himalaya (Sikkim and Arunachal Pradesh). The glaciers in the Himalaya are mainly valley glaciers bounded by high peaks. Rockfall from the steep sides makes these glaciers covered with debris, especially on the ablation side (Singh 2000; Takeuchi et al. 2000). The glaciers in the Indian Himalaya are located at an average altitude ~5360 m above sea level (asl), with the highest altitude values in the Central Himalaya (~5600) and the lowest altitude in the Western Himalaya (~5150 m) (Bolch et al., 2012). The climate in the region is influenced by the Asian monsoon and Westerlies (Bookhagen., 2010). The Eastern and Central Himalaya glaciers are mostly summer-accumulation types (Ageta & Higuchi., 1984). In the western regions, the glaciers are winter accumulation type (Quincey et al., 2011; Bolch et al., 2012). The innumerable rivers like the Indus, the Ganga, and the Brahmaputra originate from the glaciers and provide fresh water to the downstream region. According to the Geological Survey of India (GSI) inventory, there are ~9575 glaciers in the Indian part of the Himalaya (Sangewar & Shukla, 2009).

Many studies conducted in the Himalayan ranges report that glacier mass has been fluctuating since the end of the Little Ice Age (Mason, 1935; Mayewasi & Jeske 1979; Gautam and Mukherjee, 1989; Sharma & Owen, 1996; Puri and Shukla 1996; Owen, 2009; Mehta et al., 2014). The field station records from the Western Himalaya report that maximum, minimum, and seasonal average temperatures have increased by 2.8°C, 1°C ~2°C, respectively, from 1985 to 2008 (Shekhar et al., 2010). The mapping of glaciers in the Indian Himalaya was initiated at the end of the 19th century with the help of the Survey of India (SOI) and the GSI (Bamber and Rivera, 2007). The satellite remote sensing techniques improved the study of the Himalayan glaciers in a much broader way. The availability of declassified Corona images enhanced the mapping of glaciers in the past 4 to 5 decades (Bolch et al., 2009; Bhambri, et al., 2011; Chand & Sharma, 2016; Raj et al., 2016; Sahu & Gupta, 2020). However, the detection of change in glaciers from a historical perspective is lacking in many regions of the Himalaya. The earlier studies reported the retreat of Janapa, Jorya Garang, Narada, Bilare Bange, Karu Garang, and Baspa Bamak Glaciers by 696m, 425m, 550m, 90m, 800m, and 380m respectively during the period of 1963 to 1997 in the Western Himalaya (Kulkarni and Buch 1991; Kulkarni

1991; Krishna 2005; Bahuguna et al. 2007; Kulkarni et al., 2007;). Further, the study by Kulkarni et al., 2005 analyzed the retreat of the Parbati Glacier by 578 m/year of Western Himalaya from 1990 to 2001. In the Western Himalaya the recession of the Chhota Shigri glacier by 2.5 km and detachment of its main trunk in 1989 was reported by Kumar and Dobhal, 1994. The recession of the Gangotri glacier by Shankar and Srivastav (1999) is 1147 m during 1936–1996, whereas Mukherjee and Sangewar (2001) reported that the Gangotri glacier is receding at a rate of 2500m from 1935 to 1997. The Chorabari and Dokriani glaciers in the Central Himalaya receded by 344m (1962 to 2012) and 550m (1962 to 1995) by Dobhal 2014. The recession of Satopanth, Bhagirath Kharakh Glacier by Nainwal et al., 2008, the retreat of Millam and Khatling Glacier by Raj et al., 2011, 2014, 2017 are the other glaciers studied in the Central part of Himalaya. There is an accelerated retreat of glaciers shown in the Eastern Himalaya (Basnett et al., 2013) and some of the regions in Jammu and Kashmir (Rashid et al., 2017; Romshoo et al., 2020). The glacier mass balance is also a variable linking glacier dynamics and the climate (Meier and Tangborn, 1961; Zemp et al., 2019; Cogley, 2010; Singh et al., 2018). Mass balance is the difference between net gain and a net loss of glacier ice mass (Knight, 1999). The mass balance estimates of individual glaciers are monitored using field investigation (Bolch et al., 2012; Yao et al., 2012). Such measurements are logistically not suitable for glaciers on a large scale (Wagnon et al., 2007; Dobhal et al., 2008; Dhobal & Mehta, 2013; Mehta et al., 2011, 2012; Azam et al., 2012; 2014; Pratap et al., 2015, 2016). The field-based mass balance value is available for a few selected glaciers in the Himalaya like Chhota Shigri Glacier in the Chandra Valley (Dobhal et al. 1995; Wagnon et al. 2007; Azam *et al.*, 2012); Naradu glacier (1994 – 2003) in the Baspa basin (Koul and Ganjoo 2010), Gara glacier (1974 -1983), Gor-Garang (1977 – 1985) and Shaune Gorang (1981 – 1990) in the Himachal Pradesh. Dokriani Glacier, Tipra Bank (1981 – 1988) and Satopanth and Bhagirath Kharak in the Garhwal Himalaya (Singh et al. 2000a; Dobhal et al. 2004; Dobhal et al. 2008; Shah et al., 2019). Rulung glacier (1979 – 1981) in the Jammu and Kashmir.

Remote sensing data from laser altimeters, Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar (InSAR), and high-resolution DEMs using optical stereo imageries have improved the geodetic technique to derive the more precise elevation changes and mass balance of glaciers. This method is suitable to obtain large scale estimates of mass balance and is

widely used in different parts of the Himalaya (Berthier *et al.* 2007, Bolch *et al.* 2011, Kaab *et al.* 2012, Gardelle *et al.* 2013, Agarwal *et al.* 2017, Brun *et al.* 2017, Brun *et al.* 2019, Maurer *et al.* 2019). The other indirect methods of mass balance estimates in the Himalaya are Area Altitude Ratio (AAR), Improved AAR (IAAR), and Gravimetry (Kulkarni *et al.* 2004; Berthier *et al.*, 2007; Brahmabhatt *et al.*, 2012; Gardelle *et al.*, 2013; Vincent *et al.*, 2013; Mir *et al.*, 2014; Vijay and Braun, 2016). The regional scale estimates of glacier mass loss range between -0.26 ± 0.14 m w.e.a⁻¹ (Gardelle *et al.*, 2013) to -0.38 ± 0.04 m.w.e.a⁻¹ (Zhou *et al.*, 2018), which is below the global average as estimated by WGMS, 2017. These studies reported that the overall glacier mass balance estimates of glaciers in the Himalaya are moving towards negative values. The impacts of glacier loss and deviations in mass balance influence future hydrological extremes such as floods and droughts, and enhances the threats to the livelihoods of millions living downstream (Wijngaard *et al.*, 2017).

The recent landscape in the Himalaya is mainly formed by the repeated glacial and interglacial cycles during the Quaternary period (Fu *et al.*, 2013; Shukla & Garg, 2019; Garg *et al.*, 2019). Deglaciation has left a noticeable imprint on the glaciated mountains in terms of erosional and depositional landforms (Benn and Evans, 2014; Eugster *et al.*, 2016; Murtaza *et al.*, 2020; Singh *et al.*, 2020). However, the evolution of these landforms is poorly understood in many parts of the Himalaya due to their inaccessibility (Owen *et al.*, 2000; Gao and Liu, 2001; Vincent *et al.*, 2013; Romshoo *et al.*, 2015). The advancement of geospatial technology, with the help of high-resolution satellite data, has served to eliminate the major limitation of monitoring these glaciers and their associated landforms on a finer scale (Gao and Liu, 2001; Smith and Pain, 2009; Rashid *et al.*, 2017; Murtaza *et al.*, 2021). There are only a few studies conducted in different regions of the Himalaya to know the glacial advance (Ali and Juyal, 2013; Scherler *et al.*, 2010; Mehta *et al.*, 2014), and to reconstruct the past extent of glaciation and geomorphology (Ali and Juyal, 2013; Dubey *et al.*, 2019; Kumar *et al.*, 2020; Singh *et al.*, 2020; Murtaza *et al.*, 2021).

Independent dating techniques such as Optically Stimulated Luminescence (OSL) and Cosmogenic Radionuclide (CRN) surface exposure have been in the Himalayan region for identifying the age of glaciation and the glacial features (Owen *et al.*, 1997; Nainwal *et al.*, 2007; Mehta *et al.*, 2012). Using high-resolution imageries associated with

extensive field observations and dating techniques are the best tools to know the extent of glaciation in the Himalayan region throughout the Late Quaternary period (Mehta et al., 2012; Bali et al., 2013).

1.4 Study Area

1.4.1 Alaknanda Basin

The Alaknanda Basin (78°E to 81°E and 28° 5'N to 31° 5'N) is one of the important river basins in the Chamoli district of Garhwal, Uttarakhand Himalaya. The basin lies in the Central Himalaya constitutes a part of the famous Char Dham, Badrinath pilgrimage. The basin is surrounded by Bhagirathi in the North-west, Mandakini in the West, Pindar & Ganga in the South, and Satluj in the North. The basin is formed by the proglacial Alaknanda stream and its tributaries, which are mostly fed by snow, glacier melt, and monsoon precipitation (Singh & Hasnain, 1998). The Alaknanda stream originates from the Satopanth and Bhagirath Kharak glaciers and joins with Saraswati, Dhauliganga, Patalganga, Birehiganga, Nandakini, and Pindar streams. After Karnaprayag, the Alaknanda turns southwest and joins with river Bhagirathi at Devaprayag to form the river Ganga. Figure 1.2 shows the location and accessibility map of the Alaknanda Basin.

Figure 1.2 : Location and accessibility of Alaknanda Basin

1.4.2 Accessibility

The national highway NH-58 in Chamoli district is parallel to the Alaknanda River flowing from Mana village. The nearest railway station Haridwar is ~200km far from Chamoli. The highway has been built up with crumbly rocks, fluvio-glacial materials, and talus deposits from the valley slopes. The other important motorable road is from Gopeshwar to Kedarnath via Mandal. There are many other non-mettled roads and mule tracks connecting various parts of the study area (Sati, 2009).

1.4.3 Climate and Rainfall

The Alaknanda Basin climate varies from sub-tropical monsoon type (mild winter, hot summer) to tropical upland type (mild winter, dry winter, short warm summer). The northern, north-western, north-eastern, and western part of the basin is perennially under snow cover. The basin experiences four well-defined seasons viz. the cold winter season, (December to February), the hot weather season (March to May), southwest monsoon season (June to September) followed by post monsoon season (October to November). The average maximum and minimum temperature vary between 31°C and –2.9°C, respectively. During the Monsoon season, the basin receives a moderate amount of rainfall, which varies from low to high altitudinal ranges (1578 to 550 mm). The altitude above 4500m is permanently under snow and seasonal snow descends to 2800m during winter (Sati, 2009).

1.4.4 Geology

Lithologically, the Alaknanda River traverses through the Tethyan Sedimentary Sequence (TSS), Higher Himalayan Crystalline (HHC), and the Lesser Himalaya Metasedimentaries (LHM) (Heim and Gansser 1939. Figure 1.3: Geology and structures of the study area showing various thrusts like STDS (South Tibetan detachment system), Vaikrita Thrust (Main Central Thrust MCT I), Munsiri Thrust (Main central Thrust MCT II), Ramgarh Thrust. The Alaknanda Basin is characterised by the presence of various litho-tectonic units including sedimentary and high-grade metamorphic rocks. As seen in figure 1.3, the southern portion of the basin is dominated by limestone, phyllite, schists, and quartzites of the Lesser Himalayan series (Catlos et al. 2007; Ray and Srivastava 2010; Shukla et al., 2014).

The central portion is occupied by gneisses of the Higher Himalayan series and the meta-sediments of the Tethyan series occupy the northern portion. The high-grade metamorphic rocks from the Higher Himalayan crystalline group are named as Vaikrita Group which is lying between the South Tibetan Detachment System (STDM) and Main Central Thrust-I (MCT I) or Vaikrita thrust (Srivastava and Mitra 1994; Bhattacharya 2008; Ray and Srivastava 2010). Beneath the Vaikrita Thrust, the lower unit of the crystalline group is composed of lower-amphibolite facies, schists, and low-grade gneisses of the Lesser Himalayan crystalline sequence (LHCS). The LHCS rocks are well exposed in the Alaknanda valley from Helang (south of Joshimath) to Badrinath. Certain portions of the Lesser Himalaya have Precambrian to Palaeozoic sequences of the Damtha and Tejam groups (Celerier et al. 2009; Ray and Srivastava 2010). The geological structures in the Alaknanda Basin are tectonically active and lie in the central seismic gap. In recent times, the basin experienced major earthquakes among which the Chamoli earthquake (M 6.5) in 1999 made several damages (Rana et al, 2016).

Figure 1.3: The detailed lithology and geological structures in the Alaknanda Basin

1.4.5 Geomorphology

The Alaknanda Basin comprises high hills, mountain valleys, and deep gorges with high gradients. The upper part of the basin is comprised of structural hills and is continuously covered by snow and glaciers. The topography is highly precipitous, consisting of a series of peaks like Nandadevi, Kamet, Mana, Trishul, Chaukhamba, Dunagiri, Nandakot, Hathiparvat, Neelkanth, Nar & Narayan parvat. The slopes of these peaks are essentially covered with glaciers. These peaks are separated by deep, narrow gorges of Alaknanda, Saraswati, Dhauli Ganga, Birhi Ganga, Rishi Ganga, Kail, Pindar, Nandakini rivers. Glaciers, horned peaks, cirques, hanging valleys, etc., figure in this zone as well. Glacial and fluvial activities dominate the formation of various landforms. Major landforms are lateral moraines, terminal moraines, U-shaped glacier valleys, V-shaped fluvial valleys, river terraces, and landforms of mass wasting. The upper Alaknanda shows the radial drainage pattern and the lower parts show the trellis to the dendritic pattern.

Figure 1.4: Detailed map of Alaknanda Basin from satellite image showing the major glaciers, locations, and streams.

1.5 Previous Studies Conducted in the Basin and Research Gap

In Indian Himalaya, glacier studies started in the 18th century. Most of these studies reveal that the glaciers in the Himalaya are in a state of retreat since 1850. The initial attempt to prepare the glacier inventory in the Alaknanda Basin was conducted by GSI combined with SOI toposheets (Sangewar and Shukla, 1999). However, these inventory databases are neither in the digital format nor openly available to the public. The basin-wide studies of each glacier and its parameters are essential for an accurate estimate of glacier melt. However, such detailed studies of the Alaknanda Basin and the entire Central Himalaya are limited. The glacier inventories conducted in the basin are available till 2006 but limited to small catchments (Bhambiri et al., 2011; Kumar et al., 2020). The glacier-wise retreat and elevation changes for the two benchmark glaciers, namely the Satopanth and Bhagirath Kharak, in the basin have been reported by Ahmad and Rais (1998) and Nainwal et al., (2016). The glacier fragmentation has not been reported in the basin except for the Tipra glacier by Mehta et al., 2014. The supraglacial debris cover information and the mass balance of glaciers in the Alaknanda Basin have not been recorded except from the in-situ measurements of SPG (Shah et al., 2019). The long-term glacier-wide mass balance studies have not been reported in the many parts of the Central Himalaya other than the Gangotri glacier (Bhattacharya et al. 2016). The integration of spatial data with the ground truth evidence enhances the validation of the results and such studies are lacking in the Alaknanda Basin.

1.6 Motivation and Scope of the Present Study

The significance of the Himalayan glaciers is well known and always a topic of debate. Glacier retreats and advances are normal cyclic processes, but the rate of acceleration of glacier melt in the Himalayan region is a cause of concern. There are billions of people downstream, who rely on glacier meltwater for their daily routine. Therefore, it is important to monitor them on a large and regional scale to assess the overall health of glaciers. The lack of detailed quantitative information about glaciers on a regional scale motivated this study. Not many field investigations have been conducted in the Himalaya due to its inaccessible terrain. Thus, prompting a field investigation to validate the results obtained from satellite images. The impact of winter temperature on the glaciers in the basin is another inducement for the study. In particular, we address the following questions:

1. What are the factors influencing the glacier changes in the basin?
2. How does the regional climate variability translate into patterns of glacier reduction?
3. Finally, how can we reconstruct the past glacier extent using the erosional/depositional landforms?

The results obtained from the study are useful to model the future glacier changes and plan the hydrological aspects in the basin.

1.7 Objectives

To date, the glacier status in the Alaknanda Basin has not been studied well on a basin scale. Maintaining the records of glaciers and their dynamics is essential to know the basin's past, present, and future glacier status. The current research work is carried out with the following major objectives.

1. To develop an inventory of glaciers in the Alaknanda Basin from 1968 to 2020 and estimate the recession and area loss of the glaciers.
 - ✱ To identify the topographic parameters influencing glacier retreat and changes in debris cover area from 2000 to 2020.
 - ✱ To analyse the climatic parameters in the basin from 1968 to 2020, specifically the winter temperature.
2. To estimate the elevation, change, and mass balance of the glaciers in the basin from 2000 to 2017.
 - ✱ To estimate the ice volume of the glacier in the Alaknanda Basin.
3. To reconstruct the glaciers in the basin to know the paleo-glacier extent

Chapter 2

Manifestation of topography and climate variations on long-term glacier changes in the Alaknanda Basin of Central Himalaya, India

Abstract

High Mountain Asia covers the most extensive collection of snow and ice outside the poles. These glaciers serve as a major freshwater reservoir to almost 800 million people within the Indus, Ganges, and Brahmaputra basins. The fate and state of Himalayan glaciers in the 21st century has been debatable due to the large range in melting rates even at basin scales. Here we present a detailed analysis of glaciers in the Alaknanda Basin, Central Himalaya, starting with developing an inventory for 1968 and 2020 using high-resolution datasets of Corona and Sentinel-2A. Besides, we examine the factors influencing glacier characteristics such as length, debris cover extent, slope, aspect, and climatic variables, using high to medium resolution satellite data sets like Corona (1968) Cartosat-1(2011-2017), Sentinel-2A (2020), Landsat (2000-2020), SRTM (2000). Results show that glacier area reduced to $683 \pm 47.81 \text{ km}^2$ from $742 \pm 44.4 \text{ km}^2$, and the number of glaciers increased to 116 from 98 between 1968 - 2020. The observed changes are attributed to significant glacier melting and fragmentation in the Alaknanda Basin. The annual average recession of glaciers in the basin is $11.75 \pm 1.6 \text{ m/year}$ for the corresponding period. Also noted is a significant increase (by ~38%) in supraglacial debris cover extent of the glaciers in the basin over 2000 – 2020. Most interestingly, the glaciers, less than 5 km^2 area, with lower altitude snout, and higher slope, have registered greater area loss and higher retreat rate. Subsequent analysis of long-term temperature data suggests the winter temperature of the Alaknanda Basin has increased at $0.03 \text{ }^\circ\text{C/year}$ between 1968 and 2020. This comprehensive study combines topographic parameters and regional climatic data to reveal the pervasiveness of the deteriorating and disintegrating behavior of complex debris-covered glaciers in the Alaknanda Basin.

Keywords: Central Himalaya; Deglaciation; Glacier fragmentation; Glacier inventory; Snout recession; Supraglacial debris cover.

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2.1 Introduction

Alpine glaciers are considered primary indicators of climate change because of their high sensitivity to temperature variations. The enhanced sensitivity of mountain glaciers to climate perturbations has resulted in widespread glacier recessions since the Little Ice Age (Bolch et al., 2012; et al., 2013; Neckel et al., 2017; Shukla et al., 2017). The current state of deglaciation has severe adverse repercussions through diminished water availability (Carey et al., 2017; Immerzeel et al., 2020), rising global mean sea level (Haeberli and Weingartner, 2020), and increasing potential for natural hazards (Marzeion et al., 2014; Zemp et al., 2019). The Himalayan glaciers are a major source of freshwater for the entire South Asian region, which essentially drives large-scale irrigation and hydroelectric power generation (Bajracharya et al., 2008; Immerzeel et al., 2010; Rashid et al., 2017; Rounce et al., 2020).

Several studies conducted over different parts of the Himalaya have revealed changes in glacier area, snout position, Equilibrium Line Altitude (ELA), and the varying influence of debris-cover (Kulkarni et al., 2007; Bhambri et al., 2011; Bolch et al., 2012; Dobhal et al., 2013; Saraswat et al., 2013; Mehta et al., 2014; Nainwal et al., 2016; Agarwal et al., 2017; Bhushan et al., 2018; Garg et al., 2019; Shukla and Garg, 2019; Kumar et al. 2021). The rate at which the Himalayan glaciers are diminishing has been unprecedented over the past few decades (Bolch et al., 2012; Bahuguna et al., 2014; Patel et al., 2018; Shukla et al., 2020). The long-term glacier mass budget estimate over the Himalayan region has highlighted that the rate of mass loss is higher in the Eastern Himalaya and moderate in the Western Himalaya and Central Himalaya (Scherler et al., 2011; Kääb et al., 2012; Brun et al., 2017; Bhushan et al., 2018; Mölg et al., 2018; Shukla et al., 2020). Even though it is apparent that the Himalayan glaciers are undergoing massive changes, the correspondence between the changes and causal factors such as climatic, geological, and morphological parameters are inadequately addressed.

Interestingly, most of the studies are based on global glacier inventories, which have inherent limitations due to the mapping techniques, resolution of the images, Digital Elevation Model (DEM) used (Shukla et al., 2010, 2020; Paul et al., 2015, 2017). Significant discrepancies in glacier outlines have been reported in the few basin-scale studies that are available from different parts of the Himalaya (Kulkarni et al., 2004, 2007; Bhambri et al., 2011; Chand and Sharma, 2015). Although suited for large-scale studies,

these global inventories are not at all adequate for regional-scale analysis (Racoviteanu et al., 2015). Furthermore, most of the global glacier inventories are primarily computed using automated mapping techniques, which can be erroneous in highly debris-covered glaciers. Hence, there are mapping errors and missing glaciers in the global inventories. For example, the main benchmark glaciers Satopanth Glacier (SPG) and Bhagirath Kharak (BKG) in the Alaknanda Basin have been reported as a single glacier, and another major glacier named Saraswathi is not even included in the basin inventory of Randolph Glacier Inventory (RGI, 2017). Besides, these inventories are only available for the recent decades, since 2000. Hence, long-term analysis of glaciers is challenging using global inventories.

Given the uncertainties in the global inventories (Raina, 2009; Frey et al., 2012; Kaushik et al., 2019), and the need for accurate basin-scale glacier assessment and hydrological studies (IPCC, 2013; Shukla et al., 2020), it is critical to develop a comprehensive inventory for each Himalayan basin. Despite being a key factor affecting the accuracy of the glacier assessment, a complete long-term inventory of glaciers in the Alaknanda Basin has never been attempted (Bhambri et al. 2011; Kumar et al., 2021). In addition, nor there has been a basin-scale quantitative assessment of debris cover, except for a few glaciers like SPG and BKG (Shah et al., 2019). Further, this is the first study to connect glacier altitude variations with other topographical parameters of the basin.

In this study, we generate the most exhaustive long-term (1968 – 2020) inventory of glaciers in the Alaknanda Basin (98 glaciers above 1 km², with a total area coverage of ~742 km²) using high-resolution Corona and Sentinel-2A data. The validation of the glacier boundaries in the benchmark glaciers, Satopanth (SPG) and Bhagirath Kharakre glaciers (BKG), is performed using the Ground Control Points (GCPs) collected using Differential Global Positioning System (DGPS) from the field investigation conducted in 2019. The changes in the area and length of each glacier from 1968 to 2020 have been recorded. The main topographical parameters like slope, aspect, minimum and maximum elevation of each glacier have been derived using the high-resolution Cartosat-1 DEM. Further, supra glacier debris cover change in the basin between 2000 – 2020 has been estimated using the Landsat data. Subsequently, long-term temperature and precipitation data obtained from the CRU (Climatic Research Unit) is utilized to understand changes

in glaciers due to climate variations. The findings of this long-term investigation are of immense significance to augment the basin-scale glacier information.

2.2 Study Area

The Alaknanda Basin (AKB) is a fourth-order basin oriented North East and South West of the river Ganges. The basin lies in the Chamoli district of Garhwal Himalaya. An international border acts as its Northern boundary. The Ghaghra Basin and the Bhagirathi Basin are located in their eastern and western boundaries, respectively, while the Tarai region of Garhwal Himalaya represents the southern boundary of the AKB. The Alaknanda River originates from the Satopanth Glacier (SPG) and Bhagirath Kharak Glacier (BKG), joins the Saraswathi River at Mana, and flows South East to meet the Dhauliganga River at Joshimath.

Further downstream, the river changes direction and flows South West to meet the Bhagirathi River at Devprayag. The climate varies from Sub-tropical monsoon type (mild winter, hot) to tropical upland type (mild winter, dry winter, short warm summer) (CGWB 2010). The basin's topography consists of steep peaks like Nandadevi, Kamet, Trishul, Chaukhamba, Dunagiri, Nandakot, Hathiparvat, Neelkanth, Nar & Narayan Parvat. The slopes of these peaks are covered with glaciers. These peaks are separated by deep, narrow gorges of Alaknanda, Saraswati, Dhauli Ganga, Birhi Ganga, Rishi Ganga, Kail, Pindar, Nandakini Rivers. The rocks found here range from greenschist to lower amphibolite facies, but the most predominant ones are schists, The glaciated area of the AKB is ~833 km². The glaciers are located at an altitude of 3800 to 6300m. Figure 2.1 shows AKB, its main glaciers, and important reference locations.

Figure 2.1: Study area showing the glaciers considered for the present study in the AKB. The names of important locations and some well known glaciers are also represented.

2.3 Dataset

The data used for this study include various satellite, in situ, and hydrometeorological data. Figure Annexure 1: S1 represents the detailed flowchart of data and methodology used in this study. We have utilized the high-resolution, declassified Corona images of 1968 and Sentinel-2A imagery of 2020 to compile an inventory of glaciers in the basin. The Landsat 7(2000), Landsat 8 images (2017,2020), and Sentinel-2A (2020) are obtained from USGS Earth Explorer ([http:// earthexplorer.usgs.gov/](http://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/)). The images collected are at the end of the ablation season, thus ensuring minimal cloud and snow cover. These images quantify the changes in the area and length of glaciers from 1968 to 2020. The Cartosat-1 data, Survey of India (SOI) toposheets, and DEM (Remya et al., 2020) are utilised to rectify the Corona images and compute the basin's topographical parameters. The details of satellite data used are listed in Table 2.1.

The field data used here was collected with the help of a Trimble R6 differential Global Positioning System (accuracy of about 1 cm in the point-to-point kinematic (PPK) mode (Remya et al., 2020). The present study utilized the data to validate the snout and boundary position of the glaciers (SPG, BKG). The hydrometeorological variables, temperature, and precipitation is obtained from Climate Research Unit Time Series (CRU TS) 4.03 (<http://www.cru.uea.ac.uk/cru/data/hrg>) (on a 0.5° latitude-longitude grid) to compute the mean yearly temperature in °C and total annual precipitation in mm, for the period 1968–2020, in the AKB. We have also used (CRU) TS 4.03 data to identify the winter temperature changes from 1968-to 2020.

Table 2.1: Details of data used in the present study

Sl. No.	Data Set	Raw/Path or Image ID	Date of Acquisition	Spatial Resolution
1	Corona KH4B	DS1048-1134DA107	25-10-1968	2.7m
2	Corona KH4B	DS1048-1134DA108	25-10-1968	2.7m
3	Corona KH4B	DS1048-1134DA109	25-10-1968	2.7m
4	Corona KH4B	DS1048-1134DA110	25-10-1968	2.7m
5	Corona KH4B	DS1048-1134DA111	25-10-1968	2.7m
6	Corona KH4B	DS1048-1134DA112	25-10-1968	2.7m
7	Corona KH4B	DS1048-1134DF113	25-10-1968	2.7m
8	Cartosat-1 DEM	0256/0534 (stereo pairs)	21-09-2011	10m
9	Cartosat-1 DEM	0255/0533(stereo pairs)	04-10-2014	10m
10	Cartosat-1 DEM	0257/0536 (stereo pairs)	31-11-2014	10m
11	Cartosat-1 DEM	0256/0535 (stereo pairs)	19-10-2017	10m
12	Cartosat-1 DEM	0256/0533 (stereo pairs)	11-11-2017	10m
13	SRTM DEM	N30 e079 1arc v3	2000-feb	30m
14	Landsat7	145/39	15-09-2000	30m
15	Landsat8	145/39	16-10-2020	30m
16	Sentinel-2 (Optical)	A027801	18-10-2020	10m

2.4. Methods

2.4.1 Post-processing and Co-registration of the Satellite Images

The co-registration of the Corona images includes selecting observable, identical GCPs in both master and slave images. We have used eight Corona images acquired in 1968 to map the glaciers in the AKB. Considering the complex geometry of Corona imagery, we made subsets of Corona images for the AKB. All the subsets are co-registered based on the projective transformation of GCPs (Bhambri et al., 2011; 2012) and Cartosat images using ERDAS Imagine 2014. The GCPs are collected in stable areas, assuming no changes have occurred on the ground. Road junctions, river bends, and river junctions are taken as GCPs in satellite images. In glaciated terrain, prominent features like tributary-main glacier junctions, prominent drainage channels, lakes, linear landforms, river bends, river junctions, visible in both master and slave images, are considered for the collection of GCPs. For each Corona subset co-registration, 100 – 200 GCPs are acquired with the help of the Cartosat. To calculate positional accuracy, 20 to 30 common location points such as river junctions, lakes, and talus, are identified in the Cartosat and Corona subsets; the horizontal shift for 8 Corona images is between 8 – 10 m (around 3 – 4 pixels). After co-registration, digital image enhancements like radiometric enhancements are applied to the images for better visual interpretation. The Sentinel-2A, a level-1C product with the atmosphere reflectance corrected data are freely available in the public domain. The spatial resolution ranges from 10–60m. We used visible and NIR bands, each with 10m spatial resolution. The Landsat 7 Enhanced Thematic Mapper (ETM+) and Landsat 8 Operational Land Imager (OLI) are georeferenced and ready for use.

2.4.2 Mapping of Glacier Boundary

Delineation of glacier outline from satellite images is well-established in the literature (Kaab et al., 2002; Philip and Sah, 2004; Bolch et al., 2008; Racoviteanu et al., 2008). The satellite images acquired are displayed in false color composites (FCCs) to show maximum discrimination between landforms for better visual interpretation. The automated method uses well-known band ratio algorithms such as Normalize Difference Snow Index (NDSI) to delineate the glacier boundary (Kääb et al., 2002). Mapping of glaciers in a highly debris-covered terrain using NDSI reported some errors (Paul et al., 2013, 2015). To obtain precise boundary lines in a highly debris-covered terrain, we need to digitize them manually (Bolch et al., 2008; Racoviteanu et al., 2008; Bhambri et al.,

2011; Frey et al., 2012; Shukla and Garg 2019). Corona satellite images have a significant role in analyzing Earth's features (Fowler, 2004; Tappan et al., 2000; Dashora et al., 2007). We perform an on-screen manual delineation of glacier boundaries in the AKB. The delineation of boundaries in the historical and the recent periods is performed separately. The historical glacier outlines are mapped manually using the Corona images (1968), with the topographic map of 1965 (SOI, 1965) as a reference. We have considered several criteria to delineate the glaciers' snout position, such as dispensing meltwater streams at the end of the terminus, breaks in surface slope, spectral color differences, and the presence of a small meltwater pond (Kulkarni et al. 2007, Bhambri et al. 2011; Chand and Sharma, 2015). These considerations are based on the assumption that there might not be significant changes in the upper reaches, i.e., the accumulation zone of the glaciers in the AKB (Bhambri et. al., 2011). However, while digitizing, we ensured that the accumulation zone is consistent in both Corona and Sentinel-2A images. We also use available Cartosat-1 images as an additional reference source. The recent glacier boundaries (2020) are digitized using multi bands (SWIR-2, Red, and Green) of Sentinel-2A imagery with Google Earth as a reference source. The high-resolution Sentinel 2A images reduced the difficulty of differentiating debris-covered glacier terminus (Shukla et al., 2020). The digitized boundaries are also cross verified with the high-resolution Google Earth imageries and field data.

2.5 Validation of Snout Position and Boundary

Field validation of glacier boundaries delineated in this study is carried out on the basin's benchmark glaciers (SPG and BKG) using the DGPS points collected from the ground during the field trip conducted in 2019. Figure Annexure1.S2 represents the location of field DGPS points in the SPG and BKG.

2.6 Mapping of Supraglacial Debris Cover

The Supraglacial Debris Cover (SDC) on glaciers influences the glacier retreat area and mass balance (Bolch et al., 2008; Racoviteanu et al., 2008; Bhambri et., 2011; Scherler et al., 2011; Pratap et al., 2015). There are well-established methods that use band ratio algorithms to separate the supraglacial debris from glacier ice (Kulkarni et al. 2004; Paul et al., 2004; Racoviteanu et al., 2008; Bhambri et al. 2011; Pratibha and Kulkarni, 2018). We have computed changes in SDC of the glaciers in the AKB between 2000 to 2020, using the methodology suggested by Paul et al., 2004, and further followed by Pratibha

and Kulkarni, (2018). The satellite images of the glaciers (Landsat 7) and 2020 (Landsat 8) with minimum snow cover are acquired. To eliminate seasonal snow from the images, we have applied supervised classification of the multispectral images. This technique uses the maximum likelihood classification algorithm with training classification in selected areas (Khan et al., 2015). The algorithm is trained with the help of two classes of chosen signatures from snow and ice pixels using Arc GIS 10.1. Finally, we acquire minimum snow cover images by removing the pixels which contained snow. The classification accuracy is carried out by randomly selecting 200 samples and allotting them into the class to which the samples belong. The average classification accuracy achieved is 94.6%. The change in SDC of glaciers in the AKB is carried out using the minimum snow cover images of 2000 and 2020. Subsequently, we compute the commonly used Normal Difference Snow Index (NDSI) to differentiate ice pixels using equation (1)

$$\text{NDSI} = \frac{\text{Green reflectance} - \text{SWIR reflectance}}{\text{Green reflectance} + \text{SWIR reflectance}} \quad (1)$$

Then we apply a threshold value to NDSI to differentiate debris from ice. In this study, we have used the threshold value of 0.2 proposed by Pratibha and Kulkarni, 2018 to obtain the SDC over the glaciers in the AKB for 2000 and 2020.

2.7 Uncertainty Analysis

This section explains the uncertainty analysis conducted in the present study using different satellite data. The satellite data of Corona and Sentinel-2A are used to estimate the change in length and area of the glaciers from 1968 to 2020. The uncertainty of the glacier parameters is calculated using the method by Hall et al., 2003. The terminus uncertainty is estimated by using equation (2)

$$U_T = \sqrt{a^2 + b^2} + \sigma \quad (2)$$

Where U_T is the terminus uncertainty, a and b are the pixel resolution value (in meter) of the images used, and σ is the co-registration error. Here, we have considered ‘ a ’ as 2.7m and ‘ b ’ as 10m, which are the resolution of the Corona images and Sentinel-2A, respectively. For the Corona imagery, the registration error is 2 pixels, which is 5.4 m, and for the Sentinel-2A imagery, it is 5 m, which is half of the image’s native pixel resolution (Patel et al. 2017; Sahu and Guptasen, 2020).

The area uncertainty is estimated using different sources following Hall et al. (2003), using the following equation

$$U_A = 2 * U_T * x \quad (3)$$

where U_A is the area uncertainty of the glacier area, and x is the spatial resolution of the images used in 1968 and 2020, which are 2.7m and 10m, respectively. Using equation 3, we have calculated the uncertainty of the glacier area derived using Corona (1968) images and Sentinel-2A (2020) images separately. In addition, we followed the buffer method suggested by Granshaw and Fountain, 2006; Bolch et al., 2010; Bhambri et al., 2011, and Garg et al., 2017. The buffer size is kept as the registration error of the images used (Shukla et al., 2020). Here we have kept buffer size as 5.4 m for the Corona images and 5m for the Sentinel-2A images. The combined uncertainty of the glacier area is estimated as 6% for the Corona images and 7% for the Sentinel-2A images. The error estimation of mapping SDC is calculated using the buffer method by Bolch et al., (2010) and Pratibha and Kulkarni, (2018). We have also compared the uncertainty of SDC by delineating the debris cover area of a few glaciers identified by visual identification on 2000 and 2020 images. The overall area uncertainty of SDC obtained is 8% in 2000 and 9% in 2020 imagery.

2.8 Results

2.8.1 Glacier Inventory

The present study provides a new inventory of glaciers in the AKB for 1968 and 2020 (Figure Annexure1.S3 (a) and (b)). Table S1 provides the details of all the glaciers in the AKB in 1968 and 2020. The aspect of the glaciers in AKB is such that fewer glaciers are sloping in the cardinal directions (North (12%), South (8%), East (9%), and West (4%)) while a much greater percentage are sloping in the ordinal directions (Northeast (26%), southeast (22 %), northwest (13%) and southwest (18%)). The minimum and maximum elevation of each glacier in 1968 and 2020 are represented in Table S1. It is also interesting to note that in 1968 the glaciers in the AKB were located at an average elevation of 4270 – 6700m whereas, in 2020, the elevation range reduced to 4320 – 6710m. Also, the number of small glaciers (<5km²) has increased from 63% to 67% between 1968 and 2020. For 1968, 98 glaciers covering an area of 742 ± 44.4 km² have been identified. None of these 98 glaciers show an advancing trend, but some show variable retreating trends. The current inventory data of 2020 shows that the total glacier area has decreased to 683 ± 47.81km², but the total number of glaciers has increased to

116. This increase in the number of glaciers is due to glacier fragmentation. Out of the 15 fragmented glaciers listed in Table S1 (G8, G13, G18, G19, G28, G30, G34, G36, G37, G40, G45, G52, G55, G76, G80), two of them (G13 and G45) show multiple fragmentations. Figure 2.2 illustrates the fragmentation of Tipra Bank Glacier (TBG) (G45), one of the main glaciers in AKB, between 1968 and 2020. The TBG was a single glacier in 1968 with an area of 11.06 ± 0.66 , but in 2020 the glacier fragmented into 3 parts (G45, G45/f1, G45/f2). The area of the main glacier (G45) in 2020 is 5.16 ± 0.36 km², and the area of the three fragments is 3.38 ± 0.23 km²(G45/f1), 1.20 ± 0.08 km²(G45/f2), respectively.

Figure 2.2: Illustration of fragmentation of glaciers in the AKB. The main glacier in the AKB

2.8.2 Area Change

The change in the total glacier area of the AKB from 1968 to 2020 is 59 ± 3.83 km². Hence, 8% deglaciation has occurred in the basin within a span of 52 years. The spatial distribution of loss in the glacier area (Figure 2.3) shows that the glaciers in the upper Alaknanda region have lost more area than those in the lower region. The loss in the area

of glaciers is observed to range between 0.01 to 4.5 km². In figure 2.3, most of the glaciers in the AKB show area loss at a moderate range of 0 – 1 km² during 1968 – 2020. The magnitude of area loss observed is more prominent in the G8, G9, and G18 glaciers. In the AKB, the number of small glaciers (< 5km²) is more compared to the larger glaciers. We have further compared the relative area changes of glaciers within their area classes. Table 2 represents the area class distribution of glaciers and their corresponding percentage of area loss. Interestingly, smaller glaciers (less than 5 km²) have experienced relatively more area loss than larger glaciers. Eleven glaciers (G2, G12, G14, G23, G24, G28, G30, G67, G84, G95, G98) show more than 25% loss in the area between 1968 and 2020. All these glaciers, except G30, fall in the area class of less than 5km². The highest loss in glacier area (59.44%) has been observed in glacier number G23, while practically no loss has been observed for G63.

Table 2 .2: Glacier area loss in AKB from 1968 to 2020 represented as different classes

Sl. No.	Area Classes (km ²)	No. of Glaciers	Total Area in 1968 (km ²)	Loss in Area (1968-2020) (km ²)	Percentage of Area Loss
1	1 to 5	62	147.9 ± 8.9	17.6 ± 1.1	12
2	5 to 10	14	104.5 ± 6.3	9.2 ± 0.6	8.8
3	10 to 20	12	172.9 ± 10.4	12 ± 0.8	6.9
4	above 20	10	316.7 ± 19	20.1 ± 1.3	6.3

Figure 2. 3: The spatial distribution of area loss of all glaciers in the AKB from 1968 to 2020.

2.8.3 Length Change

The total change in the length of glaciers in the AKB, between 1968 and 2020, is 59.5 ± 8.7 km, which is $\sim 10\%$ of the total length of the glaciers. The annual average recession

of the total glaciers in the basin is about 11.75 ± 1.6 m per year. Figure 2.4 illustrates the length changes of selected glaciers between 1968 and 2020. In figure 2.4, the G23 glacier shows the highest retreat of 3.56 ± 0.46 km in the AKB, i.e., ~59% loss of its total length, and it is retreating at a rate of 66.46 ± 9.63 m/yr. The other fast retreating glaciers are G36 and G23, with retreat rates of 40.33 ± 5.84 m/yr. and 33.03 ± 4.7 m/yr., respectively. Glacier number G15 shows the minimum retreat, with a loss in the length of 19.32 ± 2 m. Thus, only ~1% of its total length is lost between 1968 and 2020. Glaciers that retreated more than 25% are G12, G23, G24, G28, G37, G47, G67, G73, G84, G95. The retreat rate of individual glaciers is shown in Table S1.

Figure 2. 4: The glacier status of selected glaciers in the AKB in 1968 and 2020.

2.9 Topographical Parameters and SDC of Glaciers in AKB

The present study analyses the primary topographical parameters, such as slope, aspect, and elevation, to correlate them with area change and retreat of glaciers in AKB. The mean surface slope and aspect of each glacier have been derived through satellite data (Table S1). Most of the glaciers in the basin are at a minimum of 11° and a maximum of 40° slope. Out of the 98 glaciers, 17 glaciers show a mean slope $> 25^\circ$, and the rest 81

glaciers have a mean slope of less than 25° . Figure 2.5 represents the area loss of glaciers in the AKB corresponding to their aspect. It is evident that in the AKB, the south-facing glaciers tend to shrink faster than the others. The South-facing glaciers lost around 16% of their total area, whereas the north-facing glaciers have lost only 3%. A similar, but not as prominent, tendency is noted in the northeast-facing glaciers. In these glaciers, the overall loss in the glacier area is higher than the average, which is 8%.

Figure 2. 5: The percentage of glacier area loss in the AKB from 1968 to 2020 with respect to their aspect.

The spatial extent of supraglacial debris cover (SDC) for the individual glaciers has been computed between 2000 and 2020 (Table S1), while variations in the spatial distribution are shown in Figure Annexure1.S4. In 2000, the Raikana glacier (G57) showed the highest SDC area of $19.63 \pm 1.57 \text{ km}^2$, while the glaciers G72 and G82 are clean ice glaciers with no SDC. In 2020 also G57 remained the most debris-covered glacier, with an increased area of $25.44 \pm 2.28 \text{ km}^2$, and G72 and G82 as clean ice glaciers in 2020. In 2000, the total SDC area of the glaciers in the basin is estimated to be $172.72 \pm 13.82 \text{ km}^2$. In 2020, the area increased to $239.15 \pm 21.52 \text{ km}^2$, corresponding to an

increase of ~38% over 20 years. In 2020 there are 14 glaciers (G2,G8,G9,G10,G16,G47,G50,G56,G66,G71,G74,G77,G79,G75) that shows SDC area more than 50% of the total area. Amongst these, G74 has the highest SDC of 91% in 2020 compared to the total area. Figure Annexure1.S5 represents the debris cover status of the glaciers SPG and BKG in the field.

In figure 2.6, the inset figure represents the percentage of debris cover concerning the percentage of retreat of glaciers in the AKB. The glaciers with less debris cover show higher retreat than glaciers covered with more debris, especially in the ablation region. The x-axis of figure 2.6 represents the 100m bands of snout elevation. The average percentage of retreat, area loss, and debris cover of all the glaciers with their snouts falling in each specific elevation zone is plotted against their corresponding band of snout elevation. Then the mean ablation slope for each glacier is calculated and averaged into the respective snout elevation zone, which is plotted in the secondary y-axis. In the lower elevation zones, the debris cover influences the retreat and area loss of the glaciers in the AKB. For example, the retreat and area loss in the 3950m elevation zone is relatively higher than the adjacent elevation zones (3750m and 3850m); this is probably because of the comparatively lesser SDC in the 3950m elevation zone. In 4150m, the retreat and area loss observed is minimum, the percentage of debris in this region is comparatively much higher compared to the other elevation zones. The ablation slope is also maximum in this elevation zone. In the higher elevation zones, the slope is also one of the parameters, which influences the percentage of retreat and area loss. The ablation slope is increasing from 4150m to 4850m elevation zones. The glaciers are showing moderate retreat and area loss in these zones, irrespective of being located in the higher elevation zones.

Figure 2.6: Representation of variation in the average percentage of retreat, area loss, and SDC area of glaciers with respect to the elevation of their snout. Estimates shown are the average computed over 100m elevation bands centred at altitude shown in the x axis. Also shown are the average slope of the ablation zone of glaciers with snouts located in the aforementioned 100m elevation bands. The inset figure represents the average percentage of glacier retreats with respect to their debris cover area in the AKB.

Figures 2.7a and 2.7b demonstrate the development of supraglacial, proglacial, and moraine-dammed lakes at the snout of the Raikina Glacier (G57) and Geldhung Glacier (G61) between 1968 and 2020. In figure 2.7a, the lake named Vasundhara tal near the snout of the Raikina Glacier was supraglacial in 1968, but in 2020 it became a proglacial lake, and many more supraglacial ponds are found at the snout of the Raikina Glacier. We have also validated the lake status with the help of high-resolution Google Earth images. From 2000 to 2020, the total debris cover area of the Raikina Glacier has increased by ~32%. In the Geldhung Glacier, there was no evidence of a lake at the snout in 1968 (Figure 2.7a), but in 2020 (Figure 2.7b), a prominent moraine-dammed lake is

observed near the glacier's snout. Images show that in 2000, this glacier was almost clean, but by 2020 it developed debris cover of ~24 % of the total area of the glacier.

Figure 2.7: a) The boundary of the Raikana Glacier and the Geldhung Glacier in 1968 Corona images b) The boundary of the same glaciers in 2020, delineated using Sentinel-2A and also validated using Google Earth images.

2.10 The CRU TS Long term Temperature and Precipitation Data

The CRU TS Version 4.04 Google Earth Interface data (Harris et al., 2020) is analysed over 4 grids, each named I, II, III, IV (Figure Annexure1.S6), covering the entire AKB. In Figure Annexure1. S6, I, II represent the upper AKB region, and III represents the Rishi Ganga region (a tributary of AKB), where glaciers are concentrated much in these 3 regions, and IV represents the downstream region of the AKB. Shown in Figures 8 (a) and (b) are annual average precipitation and temperature for each of the sub-regions (I to IV) of AKB from 1968 to 2020. The precipitation pattern shows a decreasing trend, and temperature shows an increasing trend from 1968-2020 for the regions (I to IV) respectively (Figure 2.8 a and b). Further, a rise in winter-time temperature has more

direct consequences on the status of glaciers. Hence, we also analyze the annual winter-time (November–March) temperature (Figure 2.8c) over 52 years, i.e., from 1968 to 2020, to ascertain its bearing on the expanse of the glaciers in the basin. The magnitude of the trend in all the analysis(9a,b,c) are determined using the Sen's Slope estimator (Sen, 1968), and the significance of the trend for the temperature dataset used here are statistically analysed using the non-parametric Modified Mann- Kendall method (Mann, 1945; Kendall, 1955; Hamed and Rao, 1998). The trend estimates are computed at a 95% confidence level ($\alpha=0.05$). In figure 2.8a, the decreasing trend of annual precipitation in AKB has been observed at a rate of 0.19mm/year, 0.18mm/year, 0.23mm/year, and 0.30mm/year in regions I, II, III, IV, respectively from 1968 to 2020. In figure 2.8b, the annual temperature of AKB has increased in all the regions (I, II, II, IV) from 1968 to 2020 at a rate of 0.02 °C/year. However, the increase in temperature is more prominent from 1990 onwards, whereas the decrease in precipitation is comparatively subtle. The winter temperature of all the regions (I, II, III, IV) in the basin (Figure 2.8c) has increased at 0.02 to 0.03°C/yr. Further, there is a noticeable change in the winter-time temperature from 2000 till the recent period.

Figure 2.8: a) Time series of annual average of a) precipitation, b) temperature and c) winter-time temperature in all the regions (I, II, III, IV). Also shown are the estimates of trends computed in each of the time series.

2.11 Discussion

The glaciers in the Himalaya have been retreating at an alarming rate for the past few decades. This study prepares a detailed inventory of glaciers for historic (1968) and contemporary (2020) periods to present the most comprehensive long-term assessment of glacier status in the AKB of Central Himalaya. Results reveal that the glaciated area reduced at $59 \pm 3.83 \text{ km}^2$, significantly larger than $18.4 \pm 9 \text{ km}^2$, reported earlier

(Bhambri et al., 2011). Concomitantly, there is an increase of individual glaciers (by 18), which is three times more than an earlier assessment (Bhambri et al., 2011). The variations in the results may be attributed to the period of analysis (i.e., 1968-2006), which is much shorter in the case of Bhambri et al., 2011. Besides, numerous studies have reported climate warming as a significant influence on the status of glaciers in recent decades (IPCC, 2021).

Most importantly, the increase in the glacier number is not due to the natural accumulation of snow and ice but due to the fragmentation of main glaciers. An earlier study by Mehta et al., 2011 reported the fragmentation of the Tipra Bank Glacier (TBG) into two parts between 1962 and 2002, with an average retreat rate of 13.4 m/yr. This study exhibits that the same TBG (G45) is fragmented into three parts with an average retreat rate of 16.97 m/yr from 1968 to 2020. The extent of SDC is one of the factors which aid glacier fragmentation in the basin, but the thicker debris cover at the lower ablation zone also impedes the glacier retreat to some extent (Kulkarni et al., 2007; Basnett et al., 2013; Dobhal et al., 2013; Pratap et al., 2015). A similar trend in deglaciation has been reported for other basins like the Bhagirathi Basin (Bhambri et al., 2011), Bhilangna Basin (Raj et al., 2017) of Central Himalaya, and Rishi Ganga Basin (one of the sub-catchments of the AKB) (Kumar et al., 2021). Overall, it is evident that Himalayan glaciers continue to shrink and retreat at rates greater than ever before. As a major freshwater reserve in the form of snow and ice, the results portray signs of adverse consequences on the population of the high mountains and the downstream riparian areas. The loss in area and length of glaciers in the Alaknanda Basin can be attributed to a combination of SDC, terrain characteristics, and climate warming.

Our observations of topographic parameters like the slope aspect, elevation range, and debris cover influence the melting rate of the glaciers in the basin. The observed glacier aspect exhibits that the south-facing glaciers experienced a loss in area 4 times (16%) greater than the north-facing (3%) glaciers. Similar results have been observed by Bhambri et al., 2011 in the Alaknanda Basin from 1968-2006 (south-facing glaciers lost ~19.4% of the area, and north-facing glaciers lost ~4.7%). In the Himalaya, south-facing glaciers are exposed to incoming solar radiation for a longer period than that of north-facing glaciers (Deota et al., 2011; Raj et al., 2017). The change in albedo due to loss of

snow cover further enhances the rate of deglaciation (Pellicciotti et al; 2008; Maurer et al., 2019; Schaefer et al., 2020; Shaw et al., 2021).

The glaciers snout in the lower altitude zone (below 4500m altitude) witness a more pronounced retreat and area loss than glaciers in the higher altitude zone. Besides, the slope of the glacier also plays a vital role in deglaciation. The glaciers with a steep slope (>20) experienced more melting than that of the gentle slope, especially in the category of small glaciers (<5 km²). The process of deglaciation may be because of their steeper slope with low debris cover area. The average surface slope of small glaciers is 21.5°, implying more area loss than the large glaciers with an average surface slope of 16 – 17° degrees. If we consider other topographic parameters to be constant, the glacier loss accelerates on a steeper slope because ice can move faster on a steeper slope than in a gentle slope. The fragmented glaciers are seen to have a steep slope (35 – 40°) at the fragmented tongues attached to the main glacier. The higher slope at these regions (mid-ablation) enhances the melting of clean ice at a faster rate when compared to the lower ablation regions with thicker debris and a gentle slope. This uneven melting pattern of ice creates slope inversion due to differential down wasting (Benn et al., 2012), which happens when the transition of glacier tongues from convex to concave up-down (Anderson and Anderson, 2018; Garg et al., 2021). Initially, the tributary glaciers contribute a minimum amount of ice to the main glaciers, and finally, there is no movement of ice from these detached tongues ('Dead ice') and further act as an independent glacier. Similar results of steeper glaciers exhibiting more deglaciation are also reported by Pandey and Venkataraman, (2013), Garg et al., (2017), and Sahu et al., (2020). The other reason for the rapid deglaciation of small glaciers is that they respond to climate change much faster compared to large glaciers (Kulkarni et al., 2007). Since the retreat and area loss of the glaciers are concentrated in the ablation region of the glacier, the snout elevation, SDC, and ablation zone slope have been observed to exercise significant controls on the retreat and area loss of glaciers in the AKB. The study noticed that the low SDC glaciers with steeper ablation slopes are retreating and shrinking at a higher rate than debris-covered glaciers with gentle slopes. A similar observation was made by Garg et al., (2017) in the Central Himalaya. Studies have revealed that a thick debris-covered glacier often undergoes a reduced melting rate than a thin debris-covered glacier or clean ice glaciers because of its insulating effect (Scherler et al., 2011; Dobhal

et al., 2013; Pratap et al., 2015). According to the present study, the debris cover in the AKB has increased by ~ 38% from 2000 to 2020. The suggested explanation for this extensive debris cover, within two decades, is the change in various factors like weathering, lithology, mass wasting, and climatic parameters. A recent study by Shukla et al., (2020) reported a 62% (1971 – 2017) debris cover change in the Suru sub-basin of Western Himalaya, and out of it, 24% of debris cover variations took place between 2000 and 2017. The supra glacier debris cover effect can create supra glacier lakes on the glacier's surface. The presence of supraglacial lakes at the glacier terminus can accelerate the rate of glacier melting and can lead to the formation of proglacial lakes (Basnett et al., 2013; Bajracharya et al., 2015; Racoviteanu et al., 2015). These lakes are also formed due to a decrease in ice flux, causing dynamic thinning and stagnant debris-covered glacier tongues (Maurer et al., 2019). This investigation has reported lake development on the Raikina Glacier and Geldhung Glacier in the AKB from 1968 to 2020.

The regional climatic parameters have a strong bearing on the glaciers in the AKB. Since there is no long-term station data available in the basin, we had to use CRU TS data to analyze the impact of hydrometeorological parameters (temperature and precipitation) in the basin. The long-term temperature data has shown an increasing trend, and the precipitation data has shown a decreasing trend in the AKB. Besides, a rise in temperature in winter can cause rapid melting of glaciers leading to significant changes in rivers. This study has observed an increase in winter temperature in the basin from 1968 to 2020, the rise in temperature being more prominent from 2000 to the current year. The area loss of glaciers, located in the upper region (I, II; Figure Annexure1.S6) of AKB experienced more than those in the lower glaciated region (III). The winter temperature is also noted to have a slight increasing trend in the upper AKB compared to the lower regions. Many studies have warned of the drastic changes in the Himalayas causing catastrophic incidents in the long run.

In the Himalaya, field studies are tedious and time-consuming due to the remote and high-altitude location of the glaciers. As a result, this study integrates satellite data with the limited in-situ observations collected from only the benchmark glaciers in the basin. It is also important to note that assessing glacier changes due to climatic variations are limited by the scarcity of weather stations in the HMA. However, this could be overcome if more stations are established in Himalaya and the data is publicly available.

2.12 Conclusion

This study presents the comprehensive assessment of glaciers in the AKB located in the Central Himalaya from 1968 to 2020. A detailed inventory of glaciers in the AKB is the first of its kind in the region. Results suggest significant loss (by $59 \pm 3.83 \text{ km}^2$) in the glacier area and fragmentation of glaciers over the basin between 1968 – 2020. The average retreat rate of glaciers in the basin is $11.75 \pm 1.6 \text{ m/yr}$. Among the non-climatic parameters, SDC has a major influence on the retreat and loss of the glaciers in the AKB. Results reveal that the total SDC of the AKB has increased by ~38% between 2000 and 2020. The glaciers with less debris-covered area and steep slopes show higher retreat than those with a high debris-cover and a gentle slope. The analysis of climatic parameters in the AKB suggests substantial evidence of deglaciation due to climate warming, especially since the winter temperature increased by $0.03 \text{ }^\circ\text{C/yr}$ between 1968 and 2020. Other significant findings of the present study are that the smaller glaciers are retreating faster than larger glaciers, and large glaciers are fragmenting into smaller glaciers in the AKB. Since the global average temperature has been increasing every year since the late 20th century, it is more likely that the deglaciation and fragmentation of glaciers in the Himalaya will only intensify in time. Consequently, there will be a cascading effect on the water security of the people living downstream.

Chapter 3

Glacier Mass Loss in the Alaknanda Basin, Garhwal Himalaya on a Decadal Scale

Abstract

The Himalayan glaciers significantly contribute to the largest river systems like the Indus, Ganga, and the Brahmaputra. The change in glacial area and mass can affect the mountain community and people living in the Indo-Gangetic plain. The present study adopted the geodetic method to estimate the elevation change and mass budget of 61 glaciers in the Alaknanda Basin, using the satellite data of Cartosat-1 (2011, 2014, 2017) and SRTM (2000). Besides the DEM of 1962 (SOI Toposheet) and 2000 (SRTM) is used to estimate the mass budget of Satopanth (SPG) and Bhagirath Kharak glaciers (BKG). The field debris thickness of SPG (2015-2017) is compared with the elevation change (2000-2017). Further, we have compared the mass loss of the glaciers with their volume. The results suggest the sustained mass loss of 1.85 ± 0.10 Gt out of 33.9 ± 8.8 Gt for 61 glaciers in the basin from 2000-2017. The mass loss of SPG and BKG during 2000-2017 is 0.20 ± 0.02 Gt and 0.24 ± 0.03 Gt, whereas from 1962 to 2000, is 0.083 ± 0.03 Gt and 0.091 ± 0.04 Gt, respectively. The analysis facilitates a better understanding of glacier mass changes in the Alaknanda Basin on a multi-decadal scale.

Keywords: “Alaknanda Basin, Debris thickness, Geodetic method, Mass budget, Satopanth Glacier.

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3.1 Introduction

Melting of ice sheets and mountain glaciers worldwide due to climate warming has played a major role in the sea level rise (IPCC 2014). The Himalayan region is known as the third pole or High Mountain Asia (HMA), and situated at the world's highest-altitude. Glaciers in the Himalaya are undergoing mass changes due to varying climatic conditions, and it has significant implications on earth's climate and regional hydrology (Bolch et al., 2012; Gardner et al., 2013). In the Western and Karakoram Himalayan regions, the glacier meltwater is not much influenced by summer monsoon when compared to the Central and Eastern Himalaya (Immerzeel et al., 2010; Bolch et al., 2012; Bhambri et al., 2013). The glacier fluctuation due to rise in temperature and reduced precipitation has affected the dynamics of glaciers in the Himalayan region, i.e., most of the glaciers have endured either retreat or thinning (Kääb et al., 2012; Yao et al., 2012; Kraaijenbrink et al., 2017; Mehta et al., 2013). These changes have influenced the populace's livelihood and well-being, living in the densely populated Himalayan range (Immerzeel et al., 2012; Tawde et al., 2017; Maurer et al., 2019). Thus, a better assessment of the mass budget will help us model the glacier meltwater runoff and future water resource management (Shean et al., 2020).

Several studies have performed mass budget computations in different parts of the Himalaya using ground-based observations (Raina et al., 1977, Azam et al., 2018, Pratap et al., 2015, Shah et al., 2019). However, those were primarily limited to a few glaciers with better accessibility (Kulkarni et al., 2004, Pratap et al., 2015). The remote sensing-based mass budget estimation (Berthier et al., 2007; Bolch et al., 2011; Kaab et al., 2012; Gardelle et al., 2013; Agarwal et al., 2017; Brun et al., 2017; Brun et al., 2019; Maurer et al., 2019) have systematically expedited the study of glaciers with a low cost to time benefit ratio. Further, enhancements in the spatial and temporal resolution of satellite images have enabled more precise mass budget computations (Kaab et al., 2012; Gardelle et al., 2013; Brun et al., 2017; Brun et al., 2019; Maurer et al., 2019; Shean et al., 2020). These current mass budget studies have been extended back in time by using declassified spy satellite photographs from the 1970s (Bolch et al., 2011; Ragettli et al., 2016; Maurer et al., 2019; King et al., 2019). The earlier studies in the Central Himalaya have revealed the glaciers with negative mean elevation changes over the period from 2000 to 2014 (Bandyopadhyay et al., 2019), with an increasing number of glaciers due to the glacier

fragmentation and most of the glaciers have undergone retreat or area loss (Bhambri et al., 2011).

The factors affecting the glacier mass loss in the Himalaya includes typically different monsoon pattern, increase in temperature due to climate warming, and to some extent the black carbon influence on the snow and ice (Salerno et al., 2015; Gertler et al., 2016; Kraaijenbrink et al., 2017). Besides, the thickness of debris mantle and the extent of debris cover has significantly affected the dynamics of the Himalayan glaciers (Gardelle et al., 2013; Pellicciotti et al., 2015; Pratap et al., 2015, Banerji et al., 2016; King et al., 2019; Maurer et al., 2019). Given the large-scale heterogeneity in their characteristic behavior, glacier fluctuation is still not understood well in the Himalaya (Kaser et al., 2006; Cogley 2009; Bolch et al., 2012; Gardelle et al., 2013). The present study computes the elevation change and mass budget estimates of 61 glaciers in the Alaknanda Basin using geodetic techniques. In addition to the contemporary period (2000–2017), this study computes the mass budget of the two largest glaciers in the basin viz., Satopanth Glacier (SPG), and Bhagirath Kharak Glacier (BKG) for the historical period of 1962–2000. The long-term investigation of glacier wide mass budget has not been reported much in the Central Himalaya other than the Gangotri glacier (Bhattacharya et al., 2016). This study's novelty includes integrating the field-based debris thickness data (Shah et al., 2019) with the elevation change obtained from satellite geodetic techniques to assess the debris thickness impact on a glacier-wide mass budget. The present analysis also provides information about glacier wide mass budget estimates, ice-thickness, and the volume of 61 glaciers in the Alaknanda Basin. Further, we have compared the glacier mass loss with their volume stored ice to access the loss of volume in the basin. The mass loss of two main glaciers SPG and BKG in the recent and historical periods is compared. The outcome of this study has important implications for an improved understanding of glacier dynamics, which would help to determine the territorial behaviour of Himalayan glaciers in response to climate change.

3.2 Study Area

The present study of the mass budget has estimated the glaciers in the Alaknanda Basin, located in the Garhwal part of Chamoli district in the Uttarakhand Himalaya (Figure 3.1). The glaciers in these ranges are generally fed by summer monsoon and winter snow (Bhambri et al., 2011, Thayyen and Gergan 2010). The Satopanth (13 km long) and

Bhagirath Kharak (18.5 km long) glaciers are the major sources of the Alaknanda River (Nainwal et al., 2008). The Alaknanda River is one of the main headstreams of river Ganga, It originates from the snout of SPG, flows downstream of Mana village where it meets the tributary river Saraswati and further flows towards Badarinath. Finally, it joins Bhagirathi River (another headstream of Ganga) at Devprayag. However, Alaknanda contributes twice as much as Bhagirathi towards the river Ganga (Singh and Hasnain 1998). The total area of the Alaknanda Basin is ~6415 km², out of which the glaciated area is ~833 km². Most of the glaciers in this region are located at an altitude range of 3800 to 6300m. According to RGI 6.0 (Randolph Glacier Inventory) database, a total of 497 glaciers are located in the Alaknanda Basin, out of which we have considered 61 glaciers (each having an area > 1 km²) covering the area of ~316 km² for the present study.

Figure 3.1. The study area of the Alaknanda Basin contains a total of 497 glaciers with their boundaries and elevation ranges. The important places in the basin are depicted in the figure. The number of glaciers in the basin is categorized with their area, and glacier hypsometry also has been given.

3.3 Materials

We have used, RGI 6.0 (<https://doi.org/10.7265/N5-RGI-60>) database to extract the boundaries of 61 glaciers used for the present study. The glacier mass budget is estimated using satellite data, reanalysis data, and in-situ data sets (Table 1).

3.3.1 Satellite Data

The Digital Elevation Models (DEM) are generated using Cartosat-1 stereo image pairs of 2011, 2014, and 2017 for the Alaknanda Basin. The Cartosat-1 satellite was launched in 2005 by the Indian Space Research Organization (ISRO) with the capability to acquire stereo image pairs. The sensor has stereoscopic cameras with a backward-looking tilt of -5° (Aft) and a forward-looking of $+26^\circ$ (Fore) (Muralikrishnan et al., 2013). The images acquired by each of these cameras have a spatial resolution of 2.5m. Subsequently, we have generated five sets of DEMs using standard photogrammetric techniques with Leica Photogrammetry Suite (LPS) in ERDAS Imagine 2014 software. The Shuttle Radar Topography Mission 2000 (SRTM) Global DEM (<https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/>) is used as a reference DEM to co-register the Cartosat-1 DEMs for mass budget calculations. The SRTM uses a C radar antenna sampled over a grid of 1 arc sec by 1 arc sec (30m) (Farr et al., 2007; Bhushan et al., 2017). The optical images of Landsat-8, Sentinel-2, and declassified images of Corona KH4B, used to extract the glacier boundaries of SPG and BKG, and Landsat-7 for the C band penetration of SRTM is obtained from the USGS website (<https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/>). Additionally, the Survey of India (SOI) toposheet is used to generate the historical DEM and boundaries of SPG and BKG glaciers for 1962.

3.3.2 In situ Data

To improve the accuracy of Cartosat-1 DEM, 14 Ground Control Points (GCP) along with the tie points are used in this study. The GCPs were acquired from the field in September 2014/15 for both the glaciers SPG and BKG (Nainwal et al., 2016) with the help of a Trimble R6 differential global positioning system (DGPS), which has an accuracy of about 1 cm in the point-to-point kinematic (PPK) mode. Then—the field measurements of debris thickness (with an accuracy of ~ 2 cm) from SPG (below 4600 m altitude) during the period 2015 to 2017 (Shah et al., 2019)—are utilized to evaluate the relationship between elevation change and debris thickness of the glacier.

3.3.3 Meteorological Data

Due to a lack of long-term weather station data in the Alaknanda Basin, we have utilized the ERA-Interim (0.25-degree resolution) global satellite reanalysis dataset of temperature and precipitation obtained from ECMFW (European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts). The ERA-Interim has better spatial resolution than other reanalysis data (Dee et al., 2011) and is widely used in the Himalayan region (Dimri et al., 2013; Li et al., 2018; Mukherjee et al., 2018). A detailed description of the data is available on the website <https://apps.ecmwf.int/datasets/data/interim-full-daily/levtype=sfc/>.

Table 3.1. Data sets and their details used for the study

Dataset	Row/Path or Image ID	Date of Acquisition	Resolution
Cartosat-I	0256/0535	19-10-2017	2.5m
Cartosat-I	0255/0533	04-10-2014	2.5m
Cartosat-I	0256/0534	21-09-2011	2.5m
Cartosat-I	0257/0536	31-11-2014	2.5m
Cartosat-I	0256/0533	11-11-2017	2.5m
SRTM	n30 e079 1arc v3	2000	30m
Landsat-8 OLI/TIRS	145/39	23-10-2017	30m
Landsat-7 ETM+	145/39	15-09-2000	30m
Sentinel-2 (Optical)	A012357	03-11-2017	10m
Corona KH4B	DS1048-1134DF109	27-09-1968	2.7m
ERA-Interim Reanalysis data	-	2000-2017	0.25°

3.4 Methods

The sequence and details of the computations performed in this study are discussed below and illustrated in Figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2: The flow chart representing the flow of data and methods followed for the present study.

3.4.1 DEM Generation

The present study generates five Cartosat-1 DEM tiles, utilizing the image pairs obtained in 2011, 2014, and 2017 (Figure 3.3). We could not acquire all these stereo image pairs for a single year because of varying snow and cloud cover. The steps involved in the DEM generation are as follows: 1) RPC camera model refinement, using bundle block adjustment, 2) stereo image alignment, using affine transformation calculated from tie-points matching across images, 3) multi-stage pyramidal stereo correlation, 4) point cloud triangulation and DEM gridding at 10 m posting. The addition of GCPs (Ground Control points) in bundle adjustment helps alleviate the pointing error of the input cameras, which can be of the order of several meters (Tian et al., 2013). In this study, GCPs collected

using DGPS on the static surfaces around SPG and BKG glaciers (Figure 3.4) are utilized during bundle adjustment.

Figure 3.3: DEM generated for the basin of 10m resolution from the Cartosat-1 stereo pairs.

Figure 3.4. DEM generated from SOI Toposheet with 100m contours are overlaid on it. The DGPS points used for the study are also represented.

3.4.2 Toposheet DEM Generation and Processing of Corona Data

The historical data includes the SOI toposheet (SOI NO.53 N\6) of 1962 at a scale of 1:50,000 and Corona KH4B images of 1968. The georectification of the toposheet is performed using ERDAS with control points (Raj 2011). The consistency of contours in the toposheet and the co-ordinates of other features present in SPG and BKG has already been confirmed by Nainwal et al., 2016. The 40 m elevation contours over glaciated and the surrounding static surfaces outside the buffer of 5 to 10 km² are manually digitized using ArcGIS 10.1. The digitized contours are interpolated using the spline interpolation technique to produce a DEM at 30 m posting (Figure 3.4). In ArcGIS software, the Topo-to-Raster tool uses the spline interpolation, which is specifically designed to work intelligently with contour lines directly to generate a surface map for DEM (ESRI 2008. http://webhelp.esri.com/arcgisdesktop/9.2/index.cfm?TopicName=Applying_a_spline_i

interpolation). Earlier studies have established that DEMs derived from toposheets have elevation patterns statistically more similar to that of SRTM (Saran et al., 2010). The georeferencing of Corona KH4B image of 1968 is performed with rectified toposheet and Cartosat-1 orthoimage (only in the stable area). The glacier area of SPG and BKG in 1962 is extracted using the toposheet and the Corona image.

3.4.3 DEM Co-registration, Estimation of Elevation Difference (dh) and Mass Budget

Initially, the SRTM DEM obtained is re-projected to Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) zone 44N to make it similar in projection to that of derived Cartosat-1 DEMs. Further, a C-Band penetration correction is performed, over snow and ice surfaces, using methods outlined in Kääb et al., 2012 and Bhushan et al., 2018. The values used here are 2.3 ± 0.6 m (1.7 ± 0.6 m) for firn/snow (clean ice) derived commonly for Himachal Pradesh, Uttarakhand, and West Nepal. The amount of penetration in the debris-covered parts of the glacier is assumed to be zero in the Alaknanda Basin. Further, using the Landsat 7 ETM⁺ data acquired on 15th September 2000, the debris area of the glacier is separated from the clean ice with the band ratio of red to short wave infrared (SWIR), i.e., Band 3/Band 5 applying the threshold of 2.2 (Vijay and Braun 2016; Bhushan et al., 2018.). Subsequently, the source Cartosat-1 and toposheet derived DEMs are individually co-registered to the reference SRTM DEM using the analytical relationship between the slope, aspect, and dh values over static surfaces in Equation 1 (Nuth and Kaab 2011) using the python package of demcoreg (Shean et al., 2019).

$$dh = a \cdot \tan \alpha \cdot \cos (b - \Psi) + dh' \quad (1)$$

where dh, α , and Ψ are representing the elevation difference, slope, and aspect, respectively. The terms a, b represents the magnitude of the horizontal shift, direction of the shift vector, and dh' denotes elevation bias between two DEMs (Nuth and Kaab 2011). Considering the source DEM as Cartosat-1 and the reference DEM as SRTM, the co-registration process is performed automatically. Initially, the Cartosat-1 DEMs resampled to maintain the same resolution of reference DEM via bicubic interpolation (Shean et al., 2016; Shean et al., 2020). The vertical and horizontal shift locations in the source DEMs have been adjusted to the reference DEM using Nuth and Kaab 2011. The detailed workflow of co-registration and the scripts are available in the co-registration

package by Shean et al., 2019. Subsequently, five sets of DEMs are co-registered, and the elevation change is derived by subtracting from one another.

Removal of outliers after generating dh for each glacier is a crucial step before calculating the mass budget. The elevation change values over glacier surface might contain some outliers due to the errors in input DEMs such as (1) inaccurate elevation values over steep slopes (Berthier et al., 2007) (2) stereo correlation artifacts over occlusions and (3) fresh featureless snow (Shean et al., 2016). We filtered the elevation values outside the mean ± 3 standard deviation range in each 100 m elevation bands over the glacier surface (Berthier et al., 2004, Gardelle et al., 2013). Subsequently, the glacier elevation change is calculated as the area-weighted average of mean elevation change over 100 m elevation bands. The elevation change estimates are converted to glacier mass balance using a constant density value of 850 kg/m^3 for ice (Cuffey and Paterson 2010).

However, we could not correct the SRTM DEM for seasonal variations due to the unavailability of long-term precipitation data in the basin. To account for that, when we have divided the period between two DEMs to get the elevation change per year of the glacier, we have included the monthly and the yearly variations between two DEMs.

3.4.4 Uncertainty Analysis

The uncertainty in glacier surface elevation changes is estimated as a combination of uncertainty in DEM differencing and uncertainty due to radar penetration (Equation 2) (Huss 2013, Bhushan et al., 2018).

$$U_{DTM} = \sqrt{(\sigma)^2 + (\Delta p)^2} \quad (2)$$

where Δp is the uncertainty in radar penetration correction, the value is taken here as 0.9 m (Kaab et al., 2012) and σ is the uncertainty of elevation change calculated over the stable ground, which is derived from equation 3 (Brun et al., 2019, Fischer et al., 2015) below:

$$\sigma_{\Delta z} \begin{cases} \sigma_{\Delta h} \sqrt{\frac{A_{cor}}{5A}} & , A < A_{cor} \\ \sigma_{\Delta h} & , A \geq A_{cor} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where $\sigma_{\Delta h}$ is the standard deviation of the rate of the elevation change on stable ground. To estimate this parameter, we have considered a 5 km^2 buffer of the stable area around each glacier. Here A is the area of the glacier and A_{cor} is defined as an effective ‘correlated’ area (Rolstad et al. 2009), which defined as $A_{cor} = \pi L^2$, with L being the decorrelation

length, taken here as 500 m (Brun et al.2017, Fischer et al. 2015). The overall uncertainty of the mass budget is estimated by using Equation 4 (Bhushan et al. 2018).

$$U_M = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\Delta h * \Delta \rho}{t * \rho_w}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{U_{DTM} * \rho_i}{t * \rho_w}\right)^2} \quad (4)$$

Here, Δh represents the observed elevation change derived over the glaciated area, t is considered the period between two DEM, $\Delta \rho$ is the uncertainty in density estimate taken as 60 kg/m^3 (Huss 2013). This procedure is applied to estimate elevation change and glacier mass budget uncertainty for every distinct period considered in the study.

The boundaries of SPG and BKG glaciers are digitized manually using ArcGIS 10.1. The errors that occurred during the digitization from the Landsat-8 and Sentinel-2 images of 2017 are estimated using Basnett et al., 2013. The uncertainty in the registration error of the Corona image and SOI toposheet is calculated using Equation 5 (Hall et al., 2003, Wang et al., 2009, Raj et al., 2017). The area uncertainty of two glaciers from the Corona image and toposheet is calculated using Equation 6 (Hall et al., 2003, Raj et al., 2017).

$$U = \sqrt{(a^2 + b^2)} + \sigma \quad (5)$$

where a , b are the pixel resolutions and σ is the registration error of the images

$$U_{area} = N_s \times A \quad (6)$$

where N_s is the number of pixels along the boundary, and A is the area of the pixels.

3.4.5 Volume Estimation

We have estimated the volume of the glaciers to compare with mass loss. The volume of each of the 61 glaciers is estimated separately using the slope dependant method proposed by Haeberli and Hoelzle (1995). The technique is used to determine the glacier volume due to simple parameterization and data availability. The results from this method have formerly compared with other ice-thickness models over the Himalaya (Frey et al., 2014, Farinotti et al., 2017). In this method, the volume of a glacier is estimated by multiplying the mean ice-thickness along the central flow line with the surface area of the glacier (Frey et al., 2014, Tawde et al., 2017). The mean ice-thickness (h_t) in meters along the central flow line is estimated using Equation 7

$$h_t = \frac{\tau}{\rho g h \sin(\alpha)} \quad (7)$$

where τ is the mean basal shear stress along the central flowline, calculated using Equation 8 (Frey et al., 2014).

$$\tau[kPa] = \begin{cases} 0.5 + 159.8 \Delta H - 43.5 (\Delta H)^2 & : \Delta H \leq 1.6 \text{ km} \\ 150 & : \Delta H > 1.6 \text{ km} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

In Equation 8, where ΔH (the difference between the maximum and minimum elevation of the glacier) is the elevation change, f is the shape factor for valley glaciers, taken as (0.8), ρ is the density of ice, α is the slope in degree and g is the gravitational acceleration. The uncertainty in the volume of glaciers is estimated by taking the fractional uncertainty of all the variables in Equation 7 (Taylor 1997; Tawde et al., 2017). The uncertainty in the shape factor f , density ρ , and basal shear stress τ is considered as 12.5%, 10%, and 29%. The slope is calculated using the ΔH and its maximum length (l). The uncertainty in slope is estimated as the root mean square error (RMSE) between the DEM derived slope and the slope calculated using $\arctan(\Delta H/l)$ (Frey et al., 2014; Tawde et al., 2017).

3.5 Results

3.5.1 Elevation Change and Mass Budget of Glaciers in the Alaknanda Basin

The mean elevation changes and mass budget of 61 glaciers are estimated using satellite geodetic techniques over varying periods (depending on data availability) ranging from 2000 to 2017. The choropleth map of Figure 3.5 and 3.6 illustrates glacier-wise elevation change and mass budget of 61 glaciers from 2000 to 2011, 2000 to 2014, and 2000 to 2017 (Table Annexure 2 : S1, S2, and S3). For the individual glacier, we observe the elevation change ranges between -0.04 m/a to -0.62 m/a. (Table S1), 0 to -0.49 m/a (Table Annexure2 S2) and -0.02 m/a to -0.92 m/a (Table Annexure2 S3) during the period of 2000-2011, 2000-2014 and 2000-2017, respectively. The mean elevation changes and mass budget of all the 61 glaciers in the Alaknanda Basin is estimated as -0.33 ± 0.08 m/a and -0.28 ± 0.08 m w.e/a respectively. The results are also compared with the previous study (Bandyopadhyay *et al.* 2019), which shows elevation change in Alaknanda Basin was -0.37 ± 0.06 m/a during 2000-2014. In both the studies, the elevation changes are estimated at 100m altitude zones.

Figure 3.5. Choropleth map depicting the elevation change (dh) of 61 glaciers in the Alaknanda Basin from the period 2000 to 2011,2014 and 2017.

Figure 3.6. Choropleth map representing the annual mass balance of 61 glaciers from 2000 to 2011,2014 and 2017.

3.5.2 The Change in the Area, Elevation, and Mass Budget of SPG and BKG

Figure 3.7 represents the spatial distribution of elevation change for SPG and BKG from 1962 to 2000 and 2000 to 2017. The change in the area of SPG from 1962 to 2017 is estimated as $3.96 \pm 0.29 \text{ km}^2$. The mean elevation changes and mass budget of SPG from 1962 to 2000 are $-0.1 \pm 0.05 \text{ m/a}$ and $-0.09 \pm 0.04 \text{ m w.e/a}$ respectively (Table 3.2). Further, the elevation changes and mass budget for SPG from 2000 to 2017 are $-0.65 \pm 0.05 \text{ m/a}$ and $-0.55 \pm 0.06 \text{ m w.e/a}$, respectively (Table 3.2). The mass budget estimate of SPG is compared with the glaciological mass budget observed from 2015 to 2017 as $-0.50 \pm 0.6 \text{ m w.e/a}$. by Shah et al., 2019.

The area changes of BKG from 1962 to 2017 is estimated to be $4.52 \pm 0.30 \text{ km}^2$. The mean elevation changes and mass budget of BKG from 1962 to 2000 are $-0.09 \pm 0.06 \text{ m/a}$, and $-0.08 \pm 0.05 \text{ m w.e/a}$, respectively. In addition, the elevation changes and mass budget for BKG from 2000 to 2017 are $-0.64 \pm 0.05 \text{ m/a}$, and $-0.54 \pm 0.06 \text{ m w.e/a}$ (Table 2). The mass budget values of SPG and BKG are showing more negative from the period 2000-2017 compared to 1962-2000. The mass loss of SPG from the period 1962-2000 and 2000-2017 are $0.083 \pm 0.03 \text{ Gt}$, and $0.20 \pm 0.02 \text{ Gt}$, respectively while the mass loss of BKG from the period 1962-2000 and 2000-2017 is $0.091 \pm 0.04 \text{ Gt}$. and $0.24 \pm 0.03 \text{ Gt}$. The loss in mass of both the glaciers is increased more than twice in recent decades compared to the historical period

Table 3.2. The elevation change and mass balance of SPG and BKG during 1962 to 2000 and 2000 to 2017 along with their change in the area observed from 1962 to 2017

RGI Id/Name	Time Period years	dh/dt (m/a)		Annual M.B (m w.e/a)		Change in Area (1962-2017) (km ²)
RGI60-15.07122/SPG	1962-2000	-0.1 ± 0.05		-0.09 ± 0.04		3.96 ± 0.29
	2000-2017	-0.65 ± 0.05		-0.55 ± 0.06		
RGI60-15.07122/BKG	1962-2000	-0.09 ± 0.06		-0.08 ± 0.05		4.52 ± 0.30
	2000-2017	-0.64 ± 0.05		-0.54 ± 0.06		

Figure 3.7. Showing the elevation change of SPG and BKG from the period 1962-2000 and 2000-2017

3.5.3 Comparison of Elevation Change and Debris Thickness

The presence of supra glacier lakes and ice-cliffs has been identified as polygons in SPG and BKG using dh value (Figure 3.8a). The lake polygons are overlaid on the 2017 satellite image and Google earth to validate the location of the lakes. Figure 3.8b represents one of the supraglacial lake locations on SPG from the field study. Figure 3.9 depicts the debris thickness rate in the ablation region of SPG per annum observed from 2015 to 2017 (Shah et al., 2019) with the corresponding elevation change per annum from the present study (2000-2017) starting from the altitude range 3800 to 4600m. The elevation change observed is more negative at the altitude range from 4400 to 4500m, where the debris concentration is minimum.

Figure 3.8a. Left image: Supraglacial lakes and cliffs located from the present study validated with the Landsat image of 2017 and Right image: The same lakes overlaid on google earth images.

Figure 3.8b. The field photograph represents one of the supra glacier lakes on SPG.

Figure 3.9. The estimated dh (2000-2017) on SPG is compared with the observed debris thickness (2015-2017) for each 50 m elevation. The thinner debris-covered zones are showing, the more negative value of dh. The maximum negative value of dh has been noticed around the altitude of 4300-4500m.

3.5.4 Ice Thickness and Volume of the Glaciers in Alaknanda Basin

The mean ice thickness and volume of 61 glaciers have been estimated individually (Table Annexure2 S4). The maximum value of ice thickness is 175.3 m for the glacier “RGI60-15.07153” and the maximum volume as 6.9 km³ for the same glacier. The minimum amount of ice thickness and volume are 26.7 m, 0.30 km³ respectively for the glacier “RGI60-15.06852”. The total ice volume of the basin covering 61 glaciers with an area of ~316 km² is estimated as 30.4 ± 9.4 Gt. The total mass loss of glaciers in the basin from 2000 to 2017 is estimated as 1.85 ± 0.10 Gt, a similar mass loss value as 1.850 ± 0.12 Gt has been reported by Bandyopadhyay et al., 2019 for the period 2000 to 2014.

3.6 Discussion

The Overall analysis of mass budget shows that the glaciers in the Alaknanda Basin are skewed towards negative, which indicates the loss of ice mass in the basin. The first assumption causing the glacier mass loss is to look into the climatic records in this region. The reanalysis data acquired over the Alaknanda Basin has no significant increase in

minimum temperature and a decrease in the total precipitation of the basin from 2000-2017 (Figure Annexure2. S1) and the details of analysis given in the supplementary section. Similar results have been reported by Bandyopadhyay et al., 2019, which shows that the mean temperature in the Alaknanda Basin has not increased much from 2000 to 2014. The comparable trends in the temperature analysis in both studies might be due to the use of reanalysis data. Whereas the other studies have reported the variations in the temperature at the different parts of Central Himalaya using the station data (Bhambri et al., 2011). The availability of reliable weather station records in the Alaknanda Basin would have improved the understanding of glacier to climate relationships in a better way. The debris effect in the basin is also one of the parameters for the mass loss of the glaciers. The debris and their concentration in the ablation region of the glaciers also influence the melting rate of ice. The earlier studies have reported an increasing number of debris-covered glaciers in the Alaknanda Basin compared to other catchments in the Central Himalaya (Bhambri et al., 2011). A more detailed investigation should be conducted to analyse the rate of debris and dynamics of the glaciers to improve the understanding of the mass loss in the Alaknanda Basin.

The mass changes of SPG and BKG from the present study show more negative from 2000 to 2017 compared to 1962-2000. The Gangotri glacier, which is located near the Alaknanda Basin, showed a mass loss of 0.29 ± 0.19 m w.e/a (2006-2014) and 0.17 ± 0.12 m w.e/a (1968-2006) by Bhattacharya et al., 2016. The studies in other parts of the Himalayan region (Mukherjee et al., 2018, Maurer et al., 2019) have reported a similar mass loss pattern.

The positive values of elevation change present in some of the ablation region of the SPG and BKG from the period 1962-2000 compared with 2000-2017. These variations can be because of the thick deposit of supra glacier debris in those elevation zones, which might have acted as an insulator for the glacier melt over the historical period. Nevertheless, over a period, the glacier response to climate change can alter the distribution of the debris thickness. There is no intermediate available DEM between 1962 to 2000 for HMA to compare the commencement of elevation change in the basin. The rate of mass budget estimated in SPG and BKG for both historical and recent periods is showing similar values. The reason for the similar mass budget values might be; these

two glaciers were joined together in the early periods. However, later they are separated through a linear ridge.

Several studies have revealed a high value of snout retreat for Himalayan glaciers on a multi-decadal scale. However, in SPG and BKG, the snout retreat rate is at a moderate value of 22.9 m/a in four decades (Nainwal et al., 2016). The present study observed that more than the snout retreat, the two glaciers are shrinking. In the Himalaya, the thickness of the debris over the glacier influences the differential melt rate of the ice (Mal et al., 2019; Mehta et al., 2013; Schmidt and Nüsser 2009; Dobhal et al., 2013; Pratap et al., 2015; Banerjee 2017). The present study has compared the debris thickness values from 2015 to 2017 with the estimated dh . We have observed that when there is a thinner layer of debris, a high negative value of dh has been identified. Based on this study and the field visit conducted in 2019 to SPG, it is observed that a thick layer of debris is deposited over the snout of the glacier, which may diminish the snout retreat. The more negative values of dh are noticed around the altitude of 4300-4500 m, where the ice-cliffs and melt ponds are observed on the glacier. The supra glacier lakes and cliffs lower the surface of the glacier more rapidly than that of clean ice (Bolch et al., 2008; Basnett et al., 2013; Raj et al., 2014; Shukla and Qadir 2016; Mal et al., 2019). In the Central Himalayan region, SPG and BKG are identified as highly debris-covered glaciers with an increasing number of supra glacier lakes and ice cliffs on the mid ablation (Laha et al., 2017; Nainwal et al., 2016). The comparison study of glacier volume to assess their mass loss is performed using the average slope and area. During 2000-2017 the 61 glaciers in the basin have undergone a loss of ~6% compared to their total ice volume.

3.7 Conclusion

In the present study, we have observed the mean elevation change, mass budget, and volume of 61 glaciers on a basin-scale from 2000 to 2017. The glacier wise assessment of elevation change, mass budget, thickness, and volume are not reported before in the Alaknanda Basin. The mass loss is observed as 6% for 61 glaciers when compared to their total volume of the basin from 2000-2017. Besides, we have estimated the long-term mass budget of two glaciers, SPG and BKG from 1962 to 2000 and 2000 to 2017. There are many variations in the mass budget observed when we compare the values from 1962 to 2000 and 2000 to 2017. The mass loss of two glaciers SPG and BKG has doubled in

recent decades than the historical periods. The debris thickness observed from the SPG 's ablation region(2015-2017) is compared with the glacier elevation change obtained from the study(2000 to 2017) to know the influence of debris on glacier surface lowering. The sustained mass loss of the two glaciers and overall mass loss of the basin from the study is an indication of the environmental changes happening to the glaciers in the basin. The behaviour of glaciers in the basin due to climate change needs to be studied in a detailed manner in the Alaknanda Basin. Also, it is vital to maintain and implement more extensive climatic station records and models in the Himalayan region, which helps to model the glaciers response to future climatic scenarios.

Chapter 4

Reconstruction of Glaciers in the Alaknanda Basin from Space and Ground Observations, Central Himalaya

Abstract

The erosional and depositional landforms modified by the glaciers can be used to reconstruct the palaeo-glacial events. However, the information about the different landform evolution and dynamics is poorly understood in many parts of the Himalaya. The present study has aimed to analyse the reconstruction of the Satopanth Glacier (SPG), Bhagirath Kharakh Glacier (BKG), and Bhagnyu Glaciers (BG) in the Alaknanda Basin of Central Himalaya. The reconstruction is carried out using the glacier morphological features such as the presence of moraines, glacial valleys, ablation valleys, hanging valleys, talus cones, which indicate the glaciers' paleo-extent. Here we have used data from the oldest toposheets of 1882 to the recent satellite images of 2020, which were supplemented by high-resolution Google Earth images and limited ground observations. The geomorphological evidence identified by the present study suggests that the basin has witnessed two significant glacial advances, Stage I and Stage II. The Stage I moraine is found at a distance of ~8.4 km from the present terminus of the glacier, while the Stage II moraines are at ~2 km. At that time the area of the trunk glacier was ~78 km² and over a period the glacier has fragmented into 3 parts with an area of 20.6 km² (SPG), 25.7 km² (BKG), and 13.6 km² (BG). The present study demonstrates significant changes in the area and length of glaciers in this basin. A thorough analysis of these changes will be crucial to understand how the glaciers evolved in time with changing climate as well as to model future glacier changes.

4.1 Introduction

The Himalayan mountains are a significant part of the cryosphere system of the world. The drastic changes of mass wasting occurring in these mountains are the key indicators of climate change (Haeberli and Beniston 2021; IPCC 2021). Considering the largest concentration of ice outside the poles, the Himalayan Mountains are considered the third pole of the world. The climate in this region is dominated by both the summer monsoon and Westerlies (Yao et al., 2012). It is well documented that most of the Himalayan

glaciers are receding at a fast pace due to climate changes (Dobhal et al, 2010, 2013; Kulkarni et al., 2007; Bagla, 2009; Ma et al., 2010; Bolch et al., 2012; Yao et al., 2012). The fluctuations of glaciers on a long-term period are controlled by their topography and regional climate (Owen et al., 2009; Mcgrath et al., 2017). Besides the end-glacial parameters like supraglacial debris and lakes can also play an important role in glacier thinning and retreat (Rowan et al., 2015; Sutherland, et al., 2020; Lee et al 2021).

The changes that occurred in the valley glaciers of the Himalaya can be used to reconstruct the past glaciation in the region. These fluctuations are demonstrated in the pattern of moraines, particularly the lateral and terminal moraines. In the Himalaya, the highest point of lateral moraines of the valley glacier coincides with the Equilibrium Line Altitude (ELA) and terminates at the snout (Nainwal et al., 2007). Collecting details about the paleo-glaciation is important in the field of global paleoclimatic research (Kääb et al., 2007; Schaefer et al., 2008). The alteration in the glacier area in different parts of the Himalaya during the historical period has been investigated by Benn and Lehmkuhl, 2000; Benn et al., 2005; Asahi, 2010; Loibl et al., 2014; Lobil and Lehmkuhl, 2015. The reconstruction of glaciers in the Central Himalaya using remote sensing techniques was attempted for only selected regions (Raj, et al., 2011, 2017; Mehta et al., 2012). In some regions of Himalaya, the glacier reconstruction is carried out using the techniques like the Optically Stimulated Luminescence (OSL) dating and other dating techniques (Sharma and Owen, 1996; Owen et al., 2002; Nainwal et al., 2007; Scherler et al., 2015).

Most of the studies indicate multiple glacial advances in the Himalaya, but the quantitative estimates of their glaciation period remained sparse. Due to the paucity of organic material in the moraines, conventional radiocarbon dating has limited use (Owen et al., 2002). However, with the advent of optically dating techniques, advancement of high-resolution satellite data, accessibility to some glacier valleys better understanding is emerging towards the factors responsible for glaciations in the Himalayan region. Nevertheless, the glacial history of large areas remains unknown and key questions of timing and extent of glaciation are not answered satisfactorily.

The field geomorphology along with satellite data and supported by OSL dating from the Mandakini River valley of the Garhwal Himalaya enabled the identification of four major glacial events in Mandakini valley for the Chorabari glacier. The Chorabari trunk glacier was extended up to ~6 km from the present terminus (Mehta et al., 2012).

Paleoglacial reconstruction based on geomorphological mapping and OSL dating in the Pindari glacier valley, Alaknanda Basin has revealed five glacial stages and reconstructed the extent of the Pindar glacier by Bali et al., 2013. Taylor and Michel (2000) have identified three glacial stages and minor advances are recognised from the Zaskar range of the north-western Indian Himalaya.

The recession gives clues for the past glacial history. Considering this, we have analysed the recession of benchmark glaciers and their paleo extent to understand the glaciation in the basin. In the present study, we have performed an exhaustive reconstruction of the main glaciers Satopanth Glacier (SPG), Bhagirath Kharakh Glacier (BKG), and the Bhagnyu Glacier (BG) in the Alaknanda Basin of Central Himalaya, to know the paleo extent of these glaciers. During the analysis, we have identified many glacial landforms, which are a prominent indication of past glaciation. This information has been utilised to reconstruct the past glacier extent of these glacier. We have used the maximum available data in the study area starting from the old topographic map (1882) to the recent Sentinel image (2020) and verified with the filed data sets and high-resolution Google Earth imageries. We have also analysed the topographic parameters influencing the glacier retreat using the high-resolution Cartosat DEM (10m). Besides, we have monitored the temperature and precipitation changes of the region for more than a century-scale (1901-2020) using the climatic data acquired from the Central Research Unit (CRU). The present study would serve as the linkage between the past and present glacial events in the Himalayan region, as glacier retreat is considered as the sensitive indicator of climate change

4.2 Study Area

The present study is conducted at Alaknanda Basin located in the Central Himalaya. The Alaknanda River is originating from the terminus of the Satopanth and Bhagirath Kharakh glaciers and meets its tributary called Sarasvati River at Mana village. The basin constitutes a total of ~433 glaciers covering an estimated area of 833km². The climate in the basin differs from sub-tropical to alpine (Sati 2009; Panwar et al., 2017). The rock types in the basin consist of main gneiss, schist, granite, migmatites, phyllite, quartzite, limestone, and dolomite. We have considered three glaciers for the present study, SPG, BGK, and BG which includes the benchmark glacier in the basin, located in the

Vishuganga basin, a sub-basin of Alaknanda. The present area of SPG, BKG, and BG is ~20.6 km², ~25.7 km², and ~13.6 km² respectively

Figure 4.1: Shows the study area map of the Alaknanda Basin with 3 main glaciers that are considered for the present study.

4.3 Material and Methods

4.3.1 Data

The old survey of India toposheets of 1882, 1936, 1954, 1962, and Corona image of 1962, 1968 has been utilised to know the glacier position in the historical period. The recent data of Cartosat-1 (2017), Cartosat DEM (2017), and the Sentinel satellite images of 2020 are used to locate the present glacier extent with the help of some geomorphological evidence. In addition, the data collected from the field expedition conducted in 2019 and the high-resolution Google Earth Imageries are utilised to confirm the results. The detailed mapping of the glacial features in the field is carried out by using the handheld Global Positioning System (GPS) and Differential Global Positioning System (DGPS) in 2019. The location of the data acquired is given in Figure 4.2. The climatic data of CRU

has been used to know the temperature and precipitation changes in the basin from 1901 to 2020. The detailed information about the data is mentioned in Table 4.1

Table 4.1: Represents the different data sources and details used for the present study

S.I No	Data Set	Raw/Path or Image ID	Date of Acquisition	Spatial Resolution	Source
1	Topographic map	53/N, Badrinath	1882	1 :250000	US Army
2	Topographic map	53/N, Badrinath	1936	1 :250000	US Army
3	Topographic map	NH 44-Dehradun	1954	1 :250000	US Army
4	SOI Toposheet	SOI NO.53 N/6	1962	1 :50000	Survey Of India
5	Corona KH4B	DS1048-1134DF109	27-09-1968	2.7m	USGS
6	Landsat7	145/39	15-09-2000	30m	USGS
7	Landsat8	145/39	16-10-2020	30m	USGS
8	Sentinel-2 (Optical)	A027801	18-10-2020	10m	USGS
9	Cartosat-1	0256/0533 (stereo pairs)	11-11-2017	2.5m	ISRO
10	Cartosat DEM		11-11-2017	10m	from stereo pairs of Cartosat-1
11	CRU TS	CRU TS v. 4.02	1901 to 2020	0.5 °	Harris et al., 2014

Figure 4.2: Represents the filed data and its details collected near the location SPG and BKG.

4.3.2 Geomorphological Mapping

The collection of glacial geomorphological evidence is primarily achieved from the old topographical sheets and followed by the satellite images of Corona, Cartosat -1, Cartosat DEM, Sentinel, and Google Earth images, along with limited field truths. The geomorphological landforms mapping is carried out by manually digitizing various features in ArcGIS 10.1 platforms with orthorectified images. We have considered the innermost prominent moraine ridge down-valley of the contemporary glacier terminus, where the ridge was often sharp-crested and with unstable and steep sides. For estimating the recession of glaciers in the Alaknanda Basin the glacier outlines belonging to different periods are overlaid in the GIS environment. To reconstruct the glaciers, the elevation points measured at different landform locations from the global positioning system (GPS) are also used. The entire erosional (U shape valley, trim lines) and depositional landforms (moraine, outwash plain, debris cones) have been marked all along the valley from the present terminus up to Mana village. In addition, supraglacial lakes and ice cliffs are manually mapped with the help of Google Earth images, and also temporal satellite imagery as an additional source.

4.3.3 Uncertainty Analysis

The mapping of glacier extent and other landforms depends on the spatial resolution of the images used. We estimated the uncertainty of the glacier mapping by the buffer method suggested by Bolch et al. (2010) and Granshaw and Fountain (2006) with the buffer width set to half the pixel resolution of the source image. The glacier terminus change uncertainty (U) was estimated as suggested by Hall et al. (2003) as:

$$UT = \sqrt{a^2 + b^2} + \sigma \quad (4)$$

Where U is the terminus uncertainty, a and b are the pixel resolution value (in meter) of the images used, and σ is the co-registration error. The area uncertainty is estimated using different sources following Hall et al. (2003), using the following equation

$$U_A = 2 * U_T * x \quad (5)$$

where U_A is the area uncertainty of the glacier area, and x is the spatial resolution of the images used.

4.4 Results and Discussions

The SPG, SPG, Bhagnyu along with its detached tributary glacier have been carved out as a distinct glacier valley with excellent glacial-geomorphological features in the upper Alaknanda Basin. The past glacier extent of these glaciers is delineated with the help of historical data (Table 1), recent satellite images, and also field evidence. The detailed results are explained as follows

4.4.1 Compound Glacier and its Tributaries

At present, SPG and BKG are two separate glaciers. However, these two glaciers were part of a trunk glacier in the past. The present study shows that the recession of the trunk glacier resulted in the splitting of the compound glacier into two valley glaciers, namely SPG and BKG in the Alaknanda Basin. Figure 4.3, represents the terminal moraine of the trunk glacier at the historical period, which is also strongly supported by the field evidence. Figure 4.3 a, b. exhibits the terminal moraine, moraine ridges, and the stream originate point identified from Corona and Cartosat images. The arc-shaped terminal moraine (Figure 4.3. a and b) are ~350m from the present snout of SPG and BKG indicates the earlier terminus location and the glacier extent. From this location, the trunk glacier receded and the recession resulted in the fragmentation of the compound glacier into two separate glaciers (SPG and BKG). Figure 4.3 c,d,e shows the field signatures of the landforms found in the satellite images (4.3a,b).

Figure 4.3: The main geomorphological features identified from the satellite images as well as from the field. In Figure 3 a & b represents the moraine details identified from the Corona (1968) and Cartosat images (2017). Figure 4, c, d & e the same features identified on the ground

4.4.2 Bhagnyu Glacier (BG)

Figure 4.4, represents the past glacier position of SPG and BKG and BG identified in the topographic maps of 1882, 1936, and 1954. The earlier terminus location of the main trunk glacier with lateral moraine is noticeable in the Corona image of 1968. It is evident from the toposheets and satellite images, supplemented by the ground observation that the BG has contributed as a tributary glacier to the main trunk glacier in the historical period (Figure 4.4). Over a period, it is detached from the main glacier trunk as a separate glacier and receding faster than SPG and BKG.

It is understood from the signatures, that this extent might have been achieved by the BG during its earlier advances which are also seen in the topographic map of 1882 (Figure 4.4a). The 1936 & 1954 topographic maps also confirmed the same (Figure 4.4b & c). The satellite image of 1968 (Figure 4.4d), shows the presence of a large talus cone/debris cone at the earlier location of the BG. The recession of the BG resulting in the release of supraglacial/englacial debris over the steep slope resulted in the formation of a talus cone, which made the debris unstable. Further, more accumulation of debris has made the talus cone grow larger up to the present extent. During the field study, the same talus cone has been observed extending from the mountain slope to the valley floor bounded by lateral moraines. The above stated evidence confirms the BG was one of the tributary glaciers contributing to the main glacier in historical time. When the trunk glacier receded, the BG got detached from the trunk glacier and becomes an independent glacier.

4.4.3 Different Stages of Glaciation

The present study confirmed two stages of glaciation in the Alaknanda Basin. Figure 4.5. shows the different glaciogenic landforms identified in the satellite and field data, which confirms stage I and II glaciations. Figures 4.5a, represent the indication of past glacier extent near the present terminus of the SPG and BKG. Further, 4.5b indicates the previous glaciation named stage II. In figure 4.5c the maximum extent of the glacier indicated by the presence of a moraine at village Mana has been identified as stage I of the glaciation.

Figure 4.4: The extent of Bhagnyu glacier in different periods a) in 1882 b) in 1936 c)1954 and d) in 1968.

The above-mentioned signatures identified from satellite data and confirmed with the presence of various erosional and depositional landforms identified in the field show that the trunk glacier was further extended downstream from its present snout location. This extent is visible in the form of a moraine (Level I) ridge at Mana. From this location, the Level I lateral moraine is discontinuous, and hence no clear evidence is observed after Mana. This Stage I of the glaciation is termed as Alaknanda glaciation by Nainwal et al, 2007.

The next set of Level II moraines was seen ~ 2km from the present terminus (Figure 4.5). This area is clearly showing many recessional moraine mounds forming the outwash plain. The location is visible in the form of an arcuate terminal moraine, wherein the river Alaknanda stream makes braided channels around these morainic mounds and also takes a sharp bending around the terminal moraine. This stage of the glaciation is Stage II glaciation and is mentioned as the Alakapuri stage by Nainwal et al., 2007.

4.4.4 Glacier Erosional and Depositional Landforms

The present study aims to map the erosional and depositional landforms associated with the glaciers from satellite data and field.

4.4.4.a Glacial Erosional Features

The “U” shaped valley with steep slopes and a flat base represents the erosive power of the trunk glacier. When a glacier moves, it erodes the sidewall as well as valley bottom and transforms into the ‘U’ shape valley. The present study utilised the Cartosat DEM to identify the profile of the glacier valley/trough. Figure 4.6a gives complete details of the elevation of the terrain and the location of the valley profiles that have been taken from the DEM. In figure 4.6.b, the profile M-N represents the ‘U’ shaped valley identified near the present terminus of the glacier. The same broad ‘U’ shaped profile has been identified in the field (Figure 4.6d). Further, profile O-P (Figure 4.6. a) has been taken near the Mana, indicating the broad ‘U’ shaped valley getting transformed into a “V” shaped valley (Figure 4.6. c). This result suggests that the broad U-shaped valley is overpowered by the fluvial activity and in some places the glaciogenic landforms are masked by fluvial landforms. Hence, we could not get many glacier landforms in this basin beyond Mana village.

Figure 4.5: Identification of glaciation stages in the satellite image of Sentinel-2 and different field evidence. In figure 5 a,b,& c represents the location where the filed photographs have been collected and the same identified in the satellite image.

In the field, it is observed that the glacial valley has a vertical cliff from the trough line, which indicates the extent of the glacier depth during its maximum advancement. The prominent feature we have identified is the presence of many hanging valleys all along the glacial valley up to Mana. The presence of these hanging valleys confirms the contribution of many tributary glaciers to the trunk glacier during its advancement. Over time, the continuous recession and surface lowering of the trunk glacier resulted in the detachment of tributary glaciers from the main trunk and left smaller valleys truncate much above the main glacial valley. These tributary valleys presently occupy high above the deeply eroded trunk valley forming as hanging valleys represented by numerous waterfalls. The meltwater from the upper snowfields contributes to these perennial waterfalls. The sahashtadhara and vasudhara waterfalls are some of the prominent hanging valley waterfalls in the Alaknanda Basin.

4.4.4.b Glacial Depositional Features

i.) Moraines

The presence of well-developed lateral, terminal and recessional moraines are identified from the satellite images and was also observed in the field. Lateral moraines are generally seen as well-defined ridges formed by the deposition of till parallel to the length of the glacier. The height of the lateral moraine is ~20 m near the present glacier boundary and ~50 near stage II. The continuity of the paleo-lateral moraines is slightly disrupted and is covered with vegetation in many places. The terminal moraines are found at the front of a glacier indicating the maximum extent of the glacier. It has been found ~1km away from the present snout of the glacier. The recessional moraines are well defined near the present terminus. A series of recessional moraines are observed between the old terminal moraine and the present terminus of SPG and BKG, developed as an outwash plain. The outwash plain holds different types of debris ranging from fine silt to boulders deposited by the meltwater streams from the glacier. In addition, some kettle lakes/ponds are also present in the outwash plain. The kettle lakes are mainly formed by the eroded depressions in which the meltwater from the glacier occupies.

Figure 4.6: Identification of different valley features (a,b,c) by taking the profile from the DEM and the same identified in the ground (d).

ii.) Ablation Valley

One striking feature observed during the study is the presence of the lateral moraine valley also referred to as ablation valley. It is mostly formed by the linear depression or sediment assemblage between the lateral moraine and the valley flank (Oestreich, 1906). The study has observed one characteristic type of lateral glacial depression called locally Chakrateerth (Figure 4.7a). It is located between the right lateral moraine of SPG and its valley walls. From the satellite imagery and field observation suggests that the Satopanth tal (lake) (Figure 4.7b) –in the basin, is also located in an ablation valley. The triangular-shaped lake is bounded by the right lateral moraine of the main SPG, the left lateral moraine of its tributary glacier, and the valley flanks. The Satopanth tal presently appears to be a blocked lake and the water contribution is mainly from the glacier melt and rainwater. The study by (Heim and Gansser, 1939), mentioned that the Chakrateerth ablation valley was occupied by a lake similar to Satopanth Tal in the past. However, the lake might have disappeared over time at present, there is no water body found nearby Chakrateerth ablation valley.

iii.) Rock Glaciers

In general, a rock glacier is a transitional phenomenon between the glacial and non-glacial processes. Rock glacier forms an important element in the permafrost and also act as a proxy for the reconstruction of the paleoclimate. Generally, the rock glaciers form in the hanging valleys as a tongue-shaped landform with rock debris having a fossil ice core. It is a lobate/ tongue shaped landform of rock debris having a series of ridges on the surface resembling a wrinkled surface with an ice core or ice cemented matrix (Bishop et al., 2011). We have observed the presence of two rock glaciers near the tributary of SPG. Figure 4.8, shows one of the rock glaciers found in the Corona image of 1968 and the same has been mapped from the recent Google Earth imagery.

Figure 4.7: Field photo of the lateral moraine valley Chakrateerth (a) and similar type valley forming the Satopanth lake(b).

Figure 4.8: A rock glacier identified near Satopanth Tal in the Corona image (1968) and also in Google Earth image

4.4.5 Glacier Reconstruction

Figure 4.9, represents the reconstructed extent of the glaciers SPG, BKG, and BG in the Alaknanda Basin. It shows the present glacier location, the paleo extent of the glacier till the Mana village, and also glacial and geomorphological landforms mapped. Table 4.2: Represents the details of the reconstruction of each glacier.

Figure 4.9: Represents the reconstructed extent of the glaciers SPG, BKG, and Bhagnyu along with their recent terminus locations. The different moraine features and each stage of glaciation are also represented in the figure. Table 4.2: Represents the details of reconstruction of each glacier

Table 4.2: Represents the details of reconstruction of each glacier

Glacier	Period	Distance (m)
SPG/BKG	Stage I- Present terminus	8410/7828
SPG/BKG	Stage II- Present terminus	1917/1316
SPG/BKG	1968- Present terminus	438/379
BG	Stage II-Present terminus	2392
BG	1968-Present terminus	524

4.5 Topographic Analysis

4.5.1 Estimation Surface Slope

The surface slope of the glaciers has been estimated with the help of DEM. The spatial distribution of the slope in each glacier is represented in Figure 4.10a. The average slope of SPG, BKG, and the BG is estimated as 19°, 16°, and 17° respectively. Further, the slope of each glacier has been plotted concerning the elevation for every 100m interval (Figure 10b, 10c, 10d). The results suggest that the slope at the ablation area of SPG and BKG is gentle but in BG it is steeper. The ablation slope of the BG is 29°, whereas for SPG and BKG is 10° and 11° respectively. The steepest slope of the BG is observed at the elevation range of 4500-5000m, the slope values are 35° to 55° respectively. This could be one of the reasons why the BG is receding and fragmenting much faster than SPG and BKG.

4.5.2 Influence on the Glacier Retreat and Supra Glacial Lakes and Ice-cliff

Further, we have mapped supraglacial lakes (SGL) and ice cliffs on the surface of the Satopanth and Bhagirath Kharak glaciers with the help of Sentinel-2 and Google Earth imageries (figure 10a). Surprisingly, the Bhagnyu glacier lacks these supraglacial features. The Satopanth and Bhagirath Kharak glaciers are highly debris-covered glaciers and their dynamics create a series of supraglacial ponds/lakes and ice cliffs. During the field study, the supraglacial lakes with ice cliffs are seen all along the ablation zone. The supraglacial lakes are dynamics and change with space and time. Due to the recession and subsequent melting, a prominent proglacial lake also formed near the terminus of the Satopanth glacier bounded by the morainic mounds.

Figure 4.10: The surface slope details the glacier SPG, BKG, and Bhagniyu and also in figures b,c, and d the slope values concerning each 100m interval.

4.6 Climatic Data

The CRU TS Version 4.04 Google Earth Interface data (Harris et al., 2020) has been used to identify the temperature and precipitation of the basin. Figure 11 (a)& (b) exhibit the annual-average precipitation and temperature of the study area of AKB from 1901 to 2020. There is an increasing trend in temperature (0.01 °C/year) and a decreasing trend in precipitation (0.1mm/year) is observed from 1901-2020 (Figure 4.11 a & b). The increase in temperature is more prominent from 1990 onwards, whereas the decrease in precipitation is comparatively subtle. The magnitude of the trend is estimated using the Sen's Slope estimator (Sen, 1968), and the significance of the trend is statistically analysed using the non-parametric Modified Mann- Kendall method (Mann, 1945; Kendall, 1955; Hamed and Rao, 1998). The trend estimates are computed at a 95% confidence level ($\alpha=0.05$).

Figure 4.11: Precipitation (a) and temperature (b) trend of the region of study from 1901-2020

4.7 Discussion

The reconstruction of SPG, BKG, and BG in the present study identified two major stages of glaciation in the Alaknanda Basin. The identified location of Stage I and Stage II glaciation are well agreeing with an earlier study by Nainwal et al 2007, which used the OSL dating method. Similar to our observation, some studies observed glacial advances & retreats on and after the LIA, indicating prominent morainic ridges on the glaciated

valleys (Raina et al. 2009; Ganjoo & Kaul 2013; Garg et al., 2019). But, contradictory to the present study, glaciers in the Karakoram Himalayas have either continued to be stable or have been advancing since the LIA (Ganju 2018; Garg et al., 2019). There are few glacier reconstruction studies conducted in the nearby basins. The studies on the Chorabari glacier in the Mandakini basin from satellite data and OSL dating showed that the trunk glacier extended up to Rambara and has four glacial stages. (Mehta 2012). In the Bhagirathi basin, the Gangotri glacier reconstructed up to 40km from the present terminus using geomorphological mapping and OSL dating using three glacial stages (Milap & Owen, 1996). Recent studies in the Bhilangna basin show two stages of glaciation and the main Khatling glacier extent was reconstructed up to 8 Km from its snout in 2016 (Raj et al, 2017).

The toposheet of 1882 acts as one of the primary sources to identify the contribution of tributary glaciers (SPG, BKG, BG) to the main trunk glacier, also supplemented by other data sources such as satellite images and limited field truths. Considering these observations, we suggest that SPG, BKG, and BG existed as tributaries of the main trunk glacier and would have extended up to the Mana village during LGM. The study by Remya et al., 2022 observed fragmentation of 15 glaciers in the Alaknanda Basin from 1968 to 2020. The various morainic deposit like lateral, terminal and recessional moraines identified near the present snout of the glaciers indicates the retreating trend of SPG, BKG, and BG in the Alaknanda Basin. The other features like boulders, kettles, glacial striations, etc found in the outwash plain indicate the past retreating phase of the glacier. The presence of hanging valleys indicates evidence of shrinkage of the glacier. A broad U-shaped glacial valley near the present snout of the Satopanth and Bhagirath Kharak glaciers is a clear indication of the erosive power of the glacier. A well-developed glacial trough with steep valley walls indicates the paleo-extent of the glacier during its advancement. This glacial valley is confirmed with the profile taken from the Cartosat DEM. The profile clearly shows the broad U-shaped valley near the terminus and U-shaped valley becoming a glacial-fluvial valley near the Mana village. This shows that fluvial activity has overridden the glacial valley.

The topographic analysis of the study mainly includes slope estimation. The altitudinal-wise slope estimation conducted by the present study enhances the identification of the steeper slope areas on the glaciers. The ablation area of the BG is

steeper and it is less covered with debris compared to SPG and BKG. There is no evidence of supraglacial lakes and ice-cliffs in the BG. The gentle slope at the ablation region and the undulating debris cover of the glacier might be one of the factors to enhance the formation of supraglacial lakes and ice cliffs in the SPG and BKG. The field visit conducted to the glaciers also confirms the undulating debris cover and stagnant supraglacial ponds and ice cliffs on the surface SPG and BKG. The climatic data analysis conducted in the study area indicates that there is a rise in temperature and reduced precipitation observed from 1901 to 2020.

Glaciers react differently with the influence of local climate; this might also result in glacier recession and fragmentation. The same has been observed by the studies conducted near the present study area, which is the Dokriani, Chorabari glacier by Mehta et al., 2014. The climate variations in the Himalaya are mainly due to the complex topography, monsoonal and westerly variation, temperature, and precipitation variation in different altitudes (Barros et al., 2006; Sanwal et al., 2013; Nag and Phartiyal, 2015; Romshoo et al., 2018; Murtaza et al., 2021). The increase in temperature in the Indian subcontinent is predicted as 3.5 and 5.5 °C by 2100 (IPCC, 2007). The present study helps to establish the time frame of glacier events in the Alaknanda Basin. Besides, the integration of glacial-geomorphic and climatic studies conducted in the basin gives a broader idea about the history of the evolution of the glaciers.

4.8 Conclusion

The present analysis exhibits the reconstruction of glaciers in the Alaknanda Basin. We have reconstructed the extent of the glaciers till Stage I moraine, which is around ~8.4 km from the present terminus of the glaciers. A detailed analysis has been conducted with the help of glacial-geomorphological evidence from the data sources such as old topographic maps (1882, 1936, 1954, 1962), Corona images of 1968, and the recent data of Landsat, Sentinel, Google Earth imageries, and remarkable landscapes in the field. The trunk glacier was much longer, wider, and thicker in the historical period. According to the present study, the satellite image signatures and the strong field evidence indicate that the glaciers in the Alaknanda Basin experienced glacial advances up to Mana village. The terminus of the trunk glacier in the past is reconstructed from the erosional and depositional landforms. The high rate of recession of glaciers in the Alaknanda Basin is

due to multiple forces acting on the glacier regime including terrain morphology, glacier dynamics, and regional climate. The various deposits of the moraines indicate contrasting recession of SPG and BKG. The presence of undulating debris cover deposits, ice cliffs, and supraglacial ponds on the surface of the glacier can increase the mass wasting activities on SPG and BKG. The retreat and fragmentation of valley glaciers into smaller glaciers will further enhance the melting of small glaciers in the basin. Such glacier loss can have a significant impact on the water security of the people living in the downstream region.

Chapter 5

Summary and Conclusion

5.1 Summary of the Results

This thesis mainly aims to analyse the recession, fragmentation, mass balance, volume, and morphological changes in the glaciers of the Alaknanda Basin, Central Himalaya. The study demonstrated here used mainly remote sensing technology for an improved understanding of the glaciers located at high, inaccessible mountains terrains. Besides, this study also integrates satellite-derived information with the limited field measurements for an in-depth understanding of the long-term evolution of some of the major glaciers in the Alaknanda Basin.

The thesis first focussed on preparing the glacier inventory of the Alaknanda Basin from 1968 to 2020. From this exhaustive inventory, glacier status and their dynamics were recorded for the first time in the Alaknanda Basin. The inventory data showed a significant loss (by $59 \pm 3.83 \text{ km}^2$) in the glacier area and fragmentation of glaciers in the basin between 1968 - 2020. The average retreat rate of glaciers in the basin was estimated as $11.75 \pm 1.6 \text{ m/yr}$. The number of glaciers in the basin increased from 98 to 116, indicating glacier fragmentation from 1968 to 2020. The supra glacier debris cover of the glaciers in the basin increased by ~38% from 2000 to 2020. The glaciers with less debris cover located at a steeper slope retreated faster than the glaciers located in a gentle slope with denser debris cover. Besides, glaciers with a smaller area located in the lower elevation ranges showed more retreat than large glaciers located at a higher range of elevation. The climatic parameters in the Alaknanda Basin show evidence of deglaciation due to an increase in temperature, especially the winter temperature, which increased by $0.03 \text{ }^\circ\text{C/yr}$ (1968-2020).

Secondly, the study focused on the estimation of glacier mass budgets on a decadal scale (2000 to 2017). The mass loss in the Alaknanda Basin was estimated at 6% for the 61 glaciers studied for the period 2000 to 2017. The glacier-wise information like elevation change, mass budget, thickness, and volume estimates were reported for the first time in the Alaknanda Basin. Further, the study intended to observe the variations in the mass budget during the historical period to the contemporary period for selected glaciers. The loss of mass in the benchmark glaciers, Satopanth and Bhagirath Karakh

during 1962-2000 was estimated as 0.083 ± 0.03 Gt and 0.091 ± 0.04 Gt, whereas from 2000-2017, it was 0.20 ± 0.02 Gt and 0.24 ± 0.03 Gt respectively. The debris thickness observed in the Satopanth glacier's ablation region (2015–2017) was compared with the glacier elevation change obtained from the study (2000–2017) to know the influence of debris on glacier surface lowering. The sustained mass loss of the two glaciers and overall mass loss of the basin from the study indicated environmental changes in the basin. The above results show that there were heterogeneous changes that occurred in the mass loss during 1962-2000 compared to 2000-2017.

Finally, the study attempted to reconstruct the glacier's past extent in the basin with the help of satellite and field observations. A detailed analysis had been conducted with the help of glacial geomorphological evidence from the data sources such as old topographic maps (1882,1936,1954,1962), Corona data of 1968, and the recent data of Landsat, Sentinel, and Google Earth imageries. Reconstruction was carried out for the main glaciers Satopanth, Bhagirath Karakh, and Bhagnyu glaciers in the basin. The reconstruction of the glaciers was performed till the glacier's stage I moraine, which is around ~8.4 km from the present terminus of the Satopanth and Bhagirath Karakh glaciers. The analysis from the satellite images and observed field evidence suggests that the glaciers in the Alaknanda Basin had undergone glacial advances up to Mana village.

During that time these three glaciers (Satopanth, Bhagirath Karakh, and Bhagnyu) were a part of the main trunk glacier. The main trunk glacier in the past was reconstructed from the erosional and depositional landforms. The thinning rate of glaciers in the Alaknanda Basin is due to multiple factors acting on the glacier including morphology of the terrain and regional climate. A fast-retreating trend of smaller glaciers and fragmentation of large glaciers had been observed in the Alaknanda Basin. Such situations profoundly impact the sustainability of Himalayan glaciers and future water availability.

5.2 Conclusion

Glaciers act as a source of freshwater for the perennial rivers downstream. Various studies have confirmed that Himalayan glaciers are in a state of retreat at multiple rates since 1960. This study was conducted to record an exhaustive inventory and mass budget of the glaciers in the Alaknanda Basin, Central Himalaya. This type of information is the first of its kind in the Alaknanda Basin. The comprehensive database of individual

glaciers includes the area, length, and topographical parameters. The glacier elevation change, the mass budget, the average ice thickness, and volume storage of 61 glaciers were reported from 2000 to 2017. This study's novelty includes the integration of field-based debris thickness with the elevation change obtained from satellite geodetic techniques, which can be used to assess the debris thickness impact on a glacier-wide mass budget. The undulating topographical terrain in the basin played a significant role in the development of deep crevasses, ice cliffs, and supraglacial lakes on the glaciers. The glaciers with steep gradients were one of the parameters, which influenced the contrasting pattern of glacier loss in the Alaknanda Basin. The retreat and fragmentation of compound glaciers into smaller glaciers will enhance the down-wasting of ice faster. Such situations will have an impact on the future sustainability of the Himalayan glaciers and freshwater availability.

The recession and mass loss of the glaciers give clues to the past glacial history. The glacial geomorphology inferred from the satellite data and field mapping confirms glacial advances in the Alaknanda Basin. The glacial valley features confirmed two stages of glacial advances post to Last Glacial Maximum (LGM). The glacier change observed in the present study when compared with the global averages suggests that the Himalayan glaciers' degradation rate appears to be in tandem with the global glacier responses. This study conducted here indicates that some glaciers are degrading faster, and their dynamics are different. The findings of this long-term investigation are of immense significance to augment the basin-scale glacier information. The global average temperature has been increasing every year since the late 20th century. It indicates that the deglaciation and fragmentation of glaciers in the Himalaya will only intensify in time. Consequently, there will be a cascading effect on the water security of the people living downstream. Although the research presented here is exclusively based on the investigations conducted in the Alaknanda Basin, the findings can help to compare the glacier dynamics in the Central Himalaya.

5.3 Future Outlook

In the Himalaya, field studies are tedious and time-consuming due to the remote and high-altitude location of the glaciers. As a result, this study integrated satellite data with the limited in-situ observations in the basin. It is also important to note that assessing glacier

changes due to climatic variations was limited by the scarcity of weather stations in the Himalyan region. We had undergone difficulties to correct our seasonality changes raised in DEM due to the unavailability of station data. However, this could be overcome if more stations are established in Himalaya and data made publicly available. The existing results from this thesis are potentially reliable for the expansion of future work in the Alkanada Basin. Furthermore, we propose exhaustive research to evaluate the role of glaciers in hydrology in the Alaknanda Basin. From the perspective of the region's water availability, the runoff from the glaciers in the basin should be evaluated. In glaciological studies, a problem is often raised concerning the empirical models. Therefore, new models and refinement of the existing methodologies for estimating ice melt are recommended. The role of debris thickness on ice melt estimates at a basin-scale needs to be incorporated on a basin scale. We planned to extend the study in the future by incorporating the dating techniques at stages I and II moraines by collecting the field samples from these locations. Unfortunately, due to the current pandemic, we could not visit the field for the last two years to get the moraine samples for dating. This sampling work will be incorporated in the coming years and will provide a strong validation point for the study of past glacial extent in the region. Other detailed investigations need to be conducted to assess the climate's impact on glacier dynamics. New automated, Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques in the extraction of information from satellite data also need to be addressed in the future. Above all, extended quantitative research on glacial melt is vital for sustaining the third pole, on which a large population relies as a permanent source of water.

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Annexure 1

Manifestation of Topography and Climate Variations on Long-term Glacier Changes in the Alaknanda Basin of Central Himalaya, India

Figure S1: Flow Chart showing the flow of data and methods used for the present study

Figure S2: The validation of the glacier boundary conducted in SPG and BKG. a) The field points collected from the ground overlaid on Sentinel-2A Imagery. b) The glacier snout of BKG in 2019 from the field photograph. c) The glacier Snout of SPG in 2019 from the filed photograph.

Figure S3: a) Glaciers delineated in the AKB for 1968, overlaid on the corona images b) The glaciers delineated for 2020, overlaid on Sentinel-2A image of 2020.

Figure S4: Illustration of the changes in the area of supraglacial debris cover (SDC) of the glaciers in the AKB for 2000 and 2020. Shown in the side panels are the magnified views of certain glaciers with major changes in SDC.

Figure S5: Supraglacial debris cover (SDC) information in Satopanth glacier (SPG) and Bhagirath Kharak glacier (BKG) as observed in the field. a) Represents the uneven distribution of SDC at the ablation zone of the SPG. b) SPG's ablation zone is mainly covered with supraglacial lakes and ice cliffs. c) debris-covered thick ice wall on the terminus position of BKG.

Figure S6: The CRU TS tiles, which have been downloaded using the Google Earth interfaces. I, II, III, IV represent the grids that are representing different portions of the AKB.

Gla _Na me	RGIId	Area in 1968 (km2)	Length in 1968 (m)	Area in 2020 (km2)	Length in 2020 (m)	Chang e in length (m)	Rate of retre at (m/y r)	Chan ge in area (km2)	Min_El evation in 1968 (m)	Min_El evation in 2020 (m)	Max _Ele vati on (m)	ME AN SLO PE (°)	Asp ect	SDC 2000 (km 2)	SDC 2020 (km2)
G1	RGI60- 15.06654	1.1	2620.9	1.00	2241.6	379.4	7.3	0.08	4410	4580	5300	20.3	NE	0.05	0.25
G2	NA	3.4	4740.1	2.22	4353.6	386.5	7.4	1.20	4000	4110	5500	21.8	S	1.00	1.11
G3	RGI60- 15.06648	3.3	4772.7	3.15	4463.2	309.4	6.0	0.11	4210	4270	5490	18.6	S	0.41	1.01
G4	RGI60- 15.06558	30.0	12731. 4	29.63	11792. 2	939.2	18.1	0.35	3800	3950	5400	13.6	E	5.03	7.19
G5	RGI60- 15.06869	1.9	2500.9	1.86	2411.1	89.8	1.7	0.05	4550	4590	5650	23.9	SE	0.32	0.33
G6	NA	1.2	2064.0	1.09	1825.6	238.5	4.6	0.15	4090	4270	5100	27.5	N	0.23	0.40
G7	RGI60- 15.06942	1.4	3146.1	1.19	2889.2	256.9	4.9	0.26	4390	4530	5900	23.9	N	0.45	0.59
G8/ SPG	RGI60- 15.07122	24.5	14047. 4	20.60	13608. 7	438.7	8.4	3.90	3800	3840	6200	20.5	NE	10.9 3	12.90
G9/ BK G	RGI60- 15.07122	30.2	20390. 1	25.69	20010. 2	379.9	7.3	4.53	3750	3780	6800	19.1	E	10.7 6	13.12
G10	NA	2.0	2330.3	1.61	2053.5	276.8	5.3	0.38	4950	5080	6050	26.9	S	1.02	1.35
G11	RGI60- 15.07190	1.3	2588.4	1.12	2567.1	21.3	0.4	0.15	4970	4990	5600	16.6	S	0.30	0.44
G12	RGI60- 15.07197	2.2	2746.8	1.36	1975.7	771.2	14.8	0.82	5200	5370	5900	20.5	S	0.02	0.10
G13	RGI60- 15.06896	16.2	6930.7	13.06	6406.7	524.0	10.1	3.11	4200	4260	6000	21.0	SE	0.67	1.24
G14	RGI60- 15.06867	1.7	1907.9	1.27	1714.1	193.8	3.7	0.43	4890	5000	5600	28.5	NE	0.03	0.18
G15	RGI60- 15.06864	2.2	2887.5	1.99	2868.2	19.3	0.4	0.19	4780	4790	5400	17.4	NE	0.27	0.51

G16	RGI60-15.06861	3.5	4373.6	3.09	3963.0	410.6	7.9	0.44	4590	4880	5510	20.0	NE	1.29	2.00
G17	RGI60-15.06860	1.3	2878.8	1.17	2723.1	155.7	3.0	0.12	5000	5010	5900	24.4	NE	0.16	0.29
G18	RGI60-15.07123	23.7	10486.0	19.59	9875.9	610.0	11.7	4.09	4710	4780	5880	16.4	NE	4.04	6.10
G19	RGI60-15.07164	12.5	8567.3	10.50	8255.0	312.3	6.0	1.98	4750	4780	5990	15.9	NE	1.53	2.30
G20	RGI60-15.07163	6.5	5446.5	6.20	4513.1	933.4	18.0	0.31	5000	5200	5900	13.3	SE	0.15	0.71
G21	RGI60-15.07165	14.3	8171.9	12.33	7047.8	1124.1	21.6	1.92	5010	5090	6300	12.2	SE	0.34	1.23
G22	RGI60-15.06845	4.2	5061.0	3.79	4678.0	383.0	7.4	0.45	5000	5090	5800	13.6	SW	0.39	0.81
G23	RGI60-15.06844	3.6	5775.8	1.47	2319.9	3455.8	66.5	2.15	4720	5200	5720	15.0	SE	0.05	0.30
G24	RGI60-15.06956	2.6	5285.6	1.63	3567.9	1717.6	33.0	0.92	4710	4980	5680	13.9	NE	0.31	0.42
G25	RGI60-15.06957	1.1	2276.6	1.04	2136.7	139.9	2.7	0.05	5160	5190	5900	18.5	N	0.01	0.13
G26	RGI60-15.06843	1.2	2121.2	1.17	2061.7	59.5	1.1	0.03	5270	5280	5730	15.8	N	0.04	0.31
G27	RGI60-15.06854	4.0	3658.7	3.95	3176.7	482.0	9.3	0.10	5380	5450	5850	12.0	E	0.06	0.83
G28	RGI60-15.06856	5.1	3399.7	2.72	2442.7	957.0	18.4	2.34	5500	5570	5880	13.3	S	0.01	0.23
G29	RGI60-15.06851	1.6	2369.5	1.45	2088.7	280.8	5.4	0.11	5250	5290	5800	15.1	NE	0.01	0.36
G30	RGI60-15.06554	7.9	5229.6	5.40	4416.4	813.2	15.6	2.45	5200	5260	5900	13.2	NE	0.31	0.81
G31	NA	10.0	6934.2	9.36	6687.2	247.0	4.8	0.60	4920	4940	6010	14.4	SE	1.40	2.39
G32	RGI60-	3.8	3039.1	3.50	2485.0	554.1	10.7	0.26	5370	5410	6100	17.4	NW	0.03	0.37

	15.06576														
G33	RGI60-15.07148	18.4	10885.4	16.78	10509.0	376.4	7.2	1.65	4990	5040	6200	16.1	SW	4.92	6.31
G34	RGI60-15.07112	22.2	10175.9	19.62	8606.3	1569.6	30.2	2.57	4750	4920	6800	15.3	SW	3.33	4.20
G35	RGI60-15.06829	1.3	2355.1	1.09	1930.5	424.6	8.2	0.16	5380	5480	5860	15.9	S	0.02	0.16
G36	RGI60-15.06826	21.1	14899.4	19.27	12802.4	2097.0	40.3	1.85	4570	4800	6100	15.8	SW	7.48	8.52
G37	RGI60-15.07071	8.0	5908.3	6.97	3632.4	2275.9	43.8	1.01	4590	4910	6000	14.7	SW	0.40	0.82
G38	RGI60-15.07072	8.8	8293.6	8.44	7398.6	895.0	17.2	0.32	4400	4490	5700	14.7	SW	2.45	3.48
G39	RGI60-15.07073	10.8	6702.1	10.47	5840.2	861.9	16.6	0.37	4520	4610	5380	16.8	W	1.84	3.14
G40	RGI60-15.07075	13.6	11667.7	13.14	10908.2	759.5	14.6	0.50	4000	4100	5700	15.7	SW	5.64	6.43
G41	RGI60-15.06801	1.3	1910.4	1.13	1531.6	378.8	7.3	0.16	4400	4650	5400	28.0	N	0.02	0.07
G42	RGI60-15.06799	1.8	2842.7	1.57	2660.0	182.7	3.5	0.21	4700	4800	5800	27.4	N	0.05	0.17
G43	NA	1.1	1558.2	1.03	1367.6	190.6	3.7	0.07	4910	4980	5400	23.8	N	0.05	0.13
G44	RGI60-15.07204	3.0	3159.0	2.83	2750.4	408.6	7.9	0.18	4530	4800	5600	19.5	NW	0.02	0.29
G45/ Tipr a Ban k	RGI60-15.06557	11.1	7432.3	10.24	6549.6	882.7	17.0	0.82	3740	3840	4800	18.5	NW	3.54	4.28
G46	RGI60-15.06791	1.7	4652.9	1.48	3687.2	965.7	18.6	0.21	3600	3900	5800	26.5	SW	0.35	0.53
G47	RGI60-	3.9	4370.7	3.41	2940.0	1430.8	27.5	0.48	4050	4320	4900	14.3	NW	1.78	2.70

	15.06560														
G48	RGI60-15.06789	4.5	3883.1	4.49	3690.1	193.0	3.7	0.03	4590	4630	5300	15.1	E	1.31	2.06
G49	RGI60-15.06559	12.0	10926.1	11.73	10057.3	868.8	16.7	0.28	3820	3950	5900	15.8	NE	3.36	4.25
G50	RGI60-15.06556	8.4	11601.5	8.30	11297.3	304.3	5.9	0.09	4180	4200	5500	12.7	SE	4.69	5.80
G51	RGI60-15.06814	2.2	2298.1	1.94	2182.8	115.3	2.2	0.22	4810	4820	5350	20.2	N	0.19	0.47
G52	RGI60-15.07153	43.3	20993.6	42.92	20710.8	282.8	5.4	0.39	4000	4090	6900	15.6	SE	16.25	20.10
G53	RGI60-15.07169	7.1	7627.3	6.92	7200.8	426.5	8.2	0.16	4500	4800	6500	15.6	S	0.09	0.71
G54	RGI60-15.06816	2.4	2847.9	2.26	2750.9	97.0	1.9	0.09	5050	5090	5500	13.4	SE	0.14	0.21
G55	RGI60-15.07168	7.2	8590.0	6.16	6543.7	2046.3	39.4	0.99	4550	4990	6150	16.6	NE	0.11	0.71
G56	RGI60-15.07151	3.0	5984.7	2.73	5375.4	609.3	11.7	0.26	4630	4750	5800	13.6	E	1.40	2.00
G57/ Raikana	RGI60-15.06977	53.9	17517.1	52.01	15395.8	2121.2	40.8	1.91	4480	4700	6200	17.5	SE	19.63	25.45
G58	RGI60-15.06819	1.7	3255.4	1.67	3181.6	73.8	1.4	0.08	5460	5490	6300	19.0	SE	0.06	0.30
G59	RGI60-15.06817	2.5	2525.6	2.23	2333.6	192.0	3.7	0.25	5450	5510	6100	17.8	SE	0.04	0.60
G60	RGI60-15.08821	3.8	5859.3	3.56	4648.8	1210.5	23.3	0.28	5100	5250	6100	18.0	NE	0.07	0.74
G61	RGI60-15.08829	2.1	4502.4	1.95	3854.5	647.9	12.5	0.11	4900	4980	5800	17.3	E	0.05	0.40
G62	RGI60-15.08839	1.2	2325.1	1.10	2057.9	267.1	5.1	0.11	5150	5170	5900	23.6	NE	0.00	0.24

G63	RGI60-15.08846	1.8	1692.8	1.80	1655.6	37.2	0.7	0.01	5100	5100	5600	19.2	N	0.01	0.39
G64	RGI60-15.08849	2.3	1847.6	2.25	1817.6	30.0	0.6	0.04	5100	5120	5500	16.8	N	0.04	0.31
G65	RGI60-15.08852	3.0	3126.0	2.96	2970.6	155.4	3.0	0.03	4600	4750	6000	24.7	NE	0.59	1.31
G66	RGI60-15.06701	7.6	11123.9	7.24	9137.2	1986.7	38.2	0.39	3870	4210	6000	20.0	N	3.24	4.40
G67	RGI60-15.06705	1.4	2735.0	1.06	1920.0	815.1	15.7	0.39	4450	4850	5400	21.6	NE	0.22	0.28
G68	RGI60-15.06706	1.3	2058.3	1.02	1895.0	163.3	3.1	0.26	4980	5100	6100	32.7	W	0.00	0.22
G69	RGI60-15.06709	5.9	4707.3	5.83	4545.0	162.4	3.1	0.07	4870	4900	6150	22.4	NW	0.70	1.91
G70	RGI60-15.06711	1.6	2753.3	1.53	2622.9	130.4	2.5	0.06	5000	5090	5900	26.2	SW	0.21	0.48
G71	RGI60-15.07025	18.5	9126.8	18.28	8540.2	586.6	11.3	0.20	4340	4400	5900	18.1	NW	7.52	10.06
G72	RGI60-15.07024	2.4	1912.2	2.38	1836.7	75.5	1.5	0.04	6400	6420	7000	26.4	W	0.00	0.00
G73	RGI60-15.06989	1.4	2605.4	1.27	1936.6	668.8	12.9	0.10	4930	5080	5700	21.1	E	0.03	0.15
G74/ Dun agiri	RGI60-15.06777	2.4	5691.4	2.40	5600.6	90.8	1.7	0.02	4230	4250	5200	11.7	N	2.12	2.19
G75	RGI60-15.06776	3.6	6189.6	3.64	6130.3	59.3	1.1	0.01	3830	3880	5600	21.7	NW	1.15	1.70
G76	RGI60-15.06774	4.2	4339.5	3.54	3593.4	746.1	14.3	0.67	5150	5250	6100	14.8	SE	1.33	1.73
G77/ Ram ni	RGI60-15.06561	9.8	9215.3	9.49	8738.3	476.9	9.2	0.29	4670	4790	5800	13.5	SW	3.35	4.88

G78	RGI60-15.06762	1.9	3697.2	1.67	3330.5	366.7	7.1	0.19	5070	5180	5900	16.2	SW	0.02	0.18
G79/ Cha ngba ng	RGI60-15.06763	5.7	6332.5	5.51	5766.3	566.2	10.9	0.15	4790	4910	6200	15.4	S	3.71	4.43
G80/ Utta ri Nan da Devi	RGI60-15.06563	31.6	16529.4	31.34	15866.6	662.8	12.7	0.27	4140	4200	6800	19.6	SW	11.2 2	13.38
G81	RGI60-15.07000	2.3	3040.1	1.92	2867.6	172.5	3.3	0.37	5150	5190	5870	40.5	SW	0.01	0.34
G82	RGI60-15.06999	1.7	3390.7	1.61	3219.4	171.3	3.3	0.10	5170	5200	6100	26.3	SW	0.00	0.13
G83	RGI60-15.07001	1.3	3450.6	1.14	3225.0	225.6	4.3	0.13	5180	5240	6600	28.9	SW	0.04	0.49
G84	RGI60-15.06768	1.6	3623.6	1.09	2588.8	1034.7	19.9	0.50	5100	5280	5900	17.6	SW	0.01	0.41
G85	RGI60-15.07301	4.1	2853.4	3.68	2316.6	536.8	10.3	0.42	5095	5220	7000	39.5	S	0.06	0.78
G86/ Dak shni Nan da Devi	RGI60-15.06727	6.8	10011.2	6.70	9797.9	213.3	4.1	0.06	4380	4400	5550	15.0	NW	4.09	5.09
G87/ Dak shni Rish	RGI60-15.07158	19.8	12421.5	19.48	11896.4	525.1	10.1	0.27	4500	4590	6700	18.6	NE	4.67	6.03

i															
G88	RGI60-15.06730	4.7	4517.6	4.26	4292.9	224.8	4.3	0.39	4990	5080	6600	24.3	NE	0.02	0.30
G89	RGI60-15.07084	2.9	4211.3	2.74	3928.1	283.2	5.4	0.12	4770	4900	6300	26.1	NE	0.05	0.42
G90	RGI60-15.06728	4.5	4061.2	4.23	3723.9	337.4	6.5	0.28	5000	5100	6600	25.7	NE	0.01	0.09
G91/ Tris hul	RGI60-15.07034	36.2	15352. 5	35.96	14300. 9	1051.6	20.2	0.26	4320	4410	6600	21.2	N	3.66	4.98
G92/ Beth ar toli	RGI60-15.07086	13.3	8014.0	13.06	7047.9	966.1	18.6	0.27	3870	4100	6300	20.1	NE	0.83	1.57
G93/ Rau nathi	RGI60-15.06564	12.5	10624. 1	11.79	8691.2	1932.9	37.2	0.67	4000	4480	6000	19.0	NW	2.63	3.56
G94	RGI60-15.07091	1.9	2830.1	1.75	2741.7	88.5	1.7	0.11	4640	4730	6700	39.0	W	0.04	0.31
G95	RGI60-15.06591	2.3	5850.3	1.57	4019.5	1830.8	35.2	0.76	3690	4070	5900	24.7	NW	0.12	0.42
G96	RGI60-15.06583	1.1	2031.1	1.08	1969.9	61.2	1.2	0.03	4830	4860	5350	26.1	SE	0.01	0.18
G97	RGI60-15.07087	1.7	4146.6	1.64	3997.1	149.5	2.9	0.06	4880	4900	6000	20.6	E	0.07	0.19
G98	RGI60-15.06579	4.6	5610.2	3.45	4355.2	1255.0	24.1	1.17	3990	4400	5600	19.7	NW	0.03	0.33

Table S1: The detailed glacier inventory of AKB in 1968 and 2020

Fragmented Glaciers	RGIId	Area (km²) 2020	Length (m) 2020	Min_Elevation in 2020 (m)	Max_Elevation (m)	MEAN SLOPE (°)	Aspect
G8/f1	RGI60-15.06943	1.29	1877.48	5500	6200	38.1	N
G13/f1	RGI60-15.06895	1.78	3007.23	5600	4780	17.13	NW
G13/f2	RGI60-15.06898	1.54	2374.16	4890	5800	22.98	NE
G13/f3	RGI60-15.06899	1.51	2062.81	4860	5800	22.43	SE
G18/f1	RGI60-15.06893	1.80	2402.27	5490	5900	15.36	E
G19/f1	RGI60-15.06889	3.25	3629.31	5350	6200	13.12	NW
G28/f1	RGI60-15.06854	1.28	2993.96	5500	5900	13.76	SE
G30/f1	RGI60-15.06852	1.03	1922.57	5450	5700	11.85	NE
G34/f1	RGI60-15.06987	8.55	9053.59	4800	6650	17.53	SW
G36/f1	RGI60-15.06834	1.59	2635.39	5420	6100	18.03	SE
G37/f1	RGI60-15.06828	2.84	4814.97	4960	5500	10.43	SE
G40/f1	RGI60-15.06800	1.37	2520.42	4410	5600	29.29	SW
G45/f1	RGI60-15.06807	3.88	4215.80	4050	5200	19.58	SE
G45/f2	RGI60-15.06808	1.20	2010.41	4600	6100	19.51	NE
G52/f1	RGI60-15.06978	3.55	4513.65	4950	5550	14.56	SE
G55/1	RGI60-15.06815	1.82	2390.87	5390	5850	20.77	NE
G76/f1	RGI60-15.07022	1.12	1897.32	5090	6200	15.54	SE
G80/f1	RGI60-15.06766	1.77	3275.53	4550	5400	23	SE

Annexure 2

Glacier mass loss in the Alaknanda basin, Garhwal Himalaya on a decadal scale

The utilization of satellite re-analysis data

Figure S1 represents the trends in monthly estimates of minimum temperature and total precipitation over the Alaknanda basin from 2000 to 2017. The magnitude and the significance of trend (95% confidence level) are estimated using the least square method and Modified Mann-Kendall method (Mann, 1945; Kendall., 1975; Hamed and Rao., 1998) respectively. The result shows minimum temperature is slightly increasing at a rate of 0.01 K/ month (p-Value > 0.05) while precipitation is decreasing at a rate of -0.05 mm/month (p-Value > 0.05) over the study area. The insignificant variations in minimum temperature and precipitation over the basin have observed.

Figure S1: . Represents the trends in monthly estimates of minimum temperature and total precipitation over the Alaknanda basin from 2000 to 2017.

Tables

Table S1, S2, and S3 contain the mean elevation change and mass budget of the glaciers from 2000 to 2011, 2014, and 2017 respectively. Table S4 represents the mean thickness and volume of 61 glaciers in the basin.

Sl. No.	RGI ID/Name	Area (km²)	dh/dt (m/a)	Annual M.B (m w.e/a)
1	RGI60-15.06557/Tipra	5.32	-0.51 ± 0.10	-0.43 ± 0.09
2	RGI60-15.06791	1.48	-0.35 ± 0.13	-0.30 ± 0.11
3	RGI60-15.06807	3.88	-0.30 ± 0.10	-0.26 ± 0.09
4	RGI60-15.06808	1.20	-0.10 ± 0.15	-0.08 ± 0.13
5	RGI60-15.06828	2.79	-0.39 ± 0.10	-0.33 ± 0.09
6	RGI60-15.06829	1.05	-0.38 ± 0.13	-0.33 ± 0.11
7	RGI60-15.07071	4.06	-0.04 ± 0.11	-0.03 ± 0.09
8	RGI60-15.07072	8.29	-0.17 ± 0.09	-0.15 ± 0.08
9	RGI60-15.07073	10.58	-0.15 ± 0.09	-0.12 ± 0.07
10	RGI60-15.07075	11.51	0.62 ± 0.09	-0.53 ± 0.08
11	RGI60-15.07153	39.60	-0.27 ± 0.08	-0.23 ± 0.07

Table S1: Annual dh and mass balance of 11 glaciers from 2000-2011

Sl.No.	RGI ID/Name	Area (km²)	dh/dt(m/a)	Annual M.B (m w.e/a)
1	RGI60-15.06553	2.66	-0.28 ± 0.07	-0.24 ± 0.06
2	RGI60-15.06554	4.29	-0.27 ± 0.07	-0.23 ± 0.06
3	RGI60-15.06829	1.05	-0.40 ± 0.09	-0.34 ± 0.08
4	RGI60-15.06843	1.17	-0.33 ± 0.08	-0.28 ± 0.07
5	RGI60-15.06851	1.48	-0.45 ± 0.08	-0.39 ± 0.07
6	RGI60-15.06852	1.14	-0.48 ± 0.10	-0.41 ± 0.09
7	RGI60-15.06854	4.22	-0.39 ± 0.07	-0.33 ± 0.06
8	RGI60-15.06856	1.44	-0.49 ± 0.08	-0.42 ± 0.08
9	RGI60-15.06956	1.63	-0.23 ± 0.08	-0.20 ± 0.07
10	RGI60-15.06957	1.04	0.00 ± 0.07	0.00 ± 0.06
11	RGI60-15.06987	8.55	-0.27 ± 0.07	-0.23 ± 0.06
12	RGI60-15.07112	7.26	-0.18 ± 0.07	-0.15 ± 0.06
13	RGI60-15.06705	1.06	-0.43 ± 0.11	-0.36 ± 0.09
14	RGI60-15.06706	1.02	-0.21 ± 0.12	-0.18 ± 0.10
15	RGI60-15.06709	5.84	-0.18 ± 0.07	-0.15 ± 0.06
16	RGI60-15.06711	1.32	-0.03 ± 0.11	-0.03 ± 0.09
17	RGI60-15.06776	3.64	-0.32 ± 0.08	-0.27 ± 0.07
18	RGI60-15.06777	2.40	-0.33 ± 0.08	-0.28 ± 0.07
19	RGI60-15.07025	18.49	-0.30 ± 0.06	-0.25 ± 0.06

Table S2: Annual dh and mass balance of 19 glaciers from 2000-2014

Sl.No.	RGI ID/Name	Area (km²)	dh/dt(m/a)	Annual M.B(m w.e/a)
1	RGI60-15.06844	1.47	-0.33 ± 0.07	-0.28 ± 0.06
2	RGI60-15.06845	3.79 8	-0.50 ± 0.06	-0.42 ± 0.06
3	RGI60-15.06861	3.09	-0.38 ± 0.05	-0.32± 0.05
4	RGI60-15.06864	1.95	-0.28 ± 0.09	-0.24 ± 0.08
5	RGI60-15.06867	1.37	-0.21 ± 0.06	-0.18 ± 0.06
6	RGI60-15.06869	1.86	-0.02 ± 0.08	-0.02± 0.07
7	RGI60-15.06893	1.80	-0.07 ± 0.07	-0.06 ± 0.07
8	RGI60-15.06895	1.81	-0.18 ± 0.07	-0.15 ± 0.06
9	RGI60-15.06896	8.24	-0.23 ± 0.06	-0.20± 0.05
10	RGI60-15.06898	1.54	-0.13 ± 0.08	-0.11 ± 0.07
11	RGI60-15.06899	1.51	-0.07 ± 0.07	-0.06 ± 0.06
12	RGI60-15.06942	1.19	-0.31 ± 0.05	-0.26 ± 0.05
13	RGI60-15.06956	1.63	-0.21 ± 0.08	-0.18 ± 0.07
14	RGI60-15.06969	1.11	-0.21 ± 0.14	-0.17 ± 0.12
15	RGI60-15.07123	17.82	-0.65 ± 0.05	-0.55 ± 0.06
16	RGI60-15.07163	6.20	-0.33 ± 0.06	-0.28 ± 0.05
17	RGI60-15.07164	7.23	-0.35 ± 0.06	-0.29 ± 0.05
18	RGI60-15.07190	1.15	-0.11 ± 0.08	-0.10± 0.07
19	RGI60-15.07122/BGK	25.70	-0.64 ± 0.05	-0.54 ± 0.06
20	RGI60-15.07122/SPG	20.4	-0.65 ± 0.05	-0.55 ± 0.06
21	RGI60-15.06556	8.30	-0.64 ± 0.06	-0.54 ± 0.06
22	RGI60-15.06557	5.32	-0.70 ± 0.06	-0.60 ± 0.07
23	RGI60-15.06559	11.74	-0.92 ± 0.06	-0.78 ± 0.07
24	RGI60-15.06807	3.88	-0.35 ± 0.07	-0.29 ± 0.06
25	RGI60-15.06808	1.20	-0.39 ± 0.10	-0.33 ± 0.09
26	RGI60-15.06814	1.94	-0.52 ± 0.07	-0.44 ± 0.07
27	RGI60-15.06815	1.82	-0.56 ± 0.08	-0.48 ± 0.07
28	RGI60-15.06816	2.26	-0.35 ± 0.07	-0.30 ± 0.07

29	RGI60-15.07151	2.73	-0.30 ± 0.07	-0.26 ± 0.06
30	RGI60-15.07168	4.35	-0.35 ± 0.07	-0.29 ± 0.06
31	RGI60-15.08829	1.96	-0.40 ± 0.09	-0.34 ± 0.08

Table S3: Annual dh and mass balance of 31 glaciers from 2000-2017

Sl.No	RGI ID	Length (km)	Thickness (m)	Area (km²)	Volume (km³)
1	RGI60-15.06557	3.955	57.084	5.320	0.304
2	RGI60-15.06791	2.429	32.582	1.482	0.048
3	RGI60-15.06807	2.166	39.628	3.884	0.154
4	RGI60-15.06808	2.225	44.018	1.199	0.053
5	RGI60-15.06828	4.736	96.286	2.788	0.268
6	RGI60-15.06829	2.499	52.277	1.049	0.055
7	RGI60-15.07071	3.790	67.333	4.058	0.273
8	RGI60-15.07072	9.186	116.806	8.293	0.969
9	RGI60-15.07073	8.334	130.165	10.584	1.378
10	RGI60-15.07075	10.743	148.424	11.510	1.708
11	RGI60-15.07153	22.205	175.239	39.603	6.940
12	RGI60-15.06553	3.986	82.934	2.660	0.221
13	RGI60-15.06554	3.490	67.674	4.288	0.290
14	RGI60-15.06829	2.499	52.277	1.049	0.055

15	RGI60-15.06843	2.313	47.504	1.172	0.056
16	RGI60-15.06851	1.954	42.259	1.477	0.062
17	RGI60-15.06852	1.160	26.653	1.142	0.030
18	RGI60-15.06854	3.090	65.969	4.219	0.278
19	RGI60-15.06856	2.292	50.242	1.436	0.072
20	RGI60-15.06956	3.677	71.064	1.630	0.116
21	RGI60-15.06957	2.231	44.972	1.043	0.047
22	RGI60-15.06987	8.582	115.447	8.552	0.987
23	RGI60-15.07112	9.310	128.381	7.258	0.932
24	RGI60-15.06705	1.908	41.338	1.060	0.044
25	RGI60-15.06706	2.000	37.261	1.018	0.038
26	RGI60-15.06709	4.334	70.316	5.835	0.410
27	RGI60-15.06711	2.571	52.146	1.324	0.069
28	RGI60-15.06776	2.078	33.094	3.637	0.120
29	RGI60-15.06777	4.666	89.215	2.400	0.214
30	RGI60-15.07025	11.334	103.124	18.493	1.907
31	RGI60-15.06844	2.352	48.431	1.470	0.071
32	RGI60-15.06845	4.714	90.565	3.792	0.343
33	RGI60-15.06861	4.243	81.849	3.090	0.253
34	RGI60-15.06864	2.056	41.003	1.947	0.080
35	RGI60-15.06867	1.418	30.617	1.373	0.042

36	RGI60-15.06869	2.398	44.439	1.857	0.083
37	RGI60-15.06893	2.390	51.376	1.801	0.093
38	RGI60-15.06895	3.224	61.590	1.812	0.112
39	RGI60-15.06896	6.563	84.017	8.244	0.693
40	RGI60-15.06898	1.707	35.042	1.544	0.054
41	RGI60-15.06899	1.744	36.389	1.506	0.055
42	RGI60-15.06942	2.079	38.616	1.189	0.046
43	RGI60-15.06956	3.677	71.064	1.630	0.116
44	RGI60-15.06969	1.923	38.440	1.112	0.043
45	RGI60-15.07123	10.605	160.761	17.821	2.865
46	RGI60-15.07163	5.092	95.855	6.199	0.594
47	RGI60-15.07164	8.642	120.255	7.225	0.869
48	RGI60-15.07190	2.568	52.678	1.145	0.060
49	RGI60-15.07122/BGK	18.793	138.823	25.695	3.567
50	RGI60-15.07122/SPG	12.408	94.267	20.400	1.923
51	RGI60-15.06556	7.887	119.110	8.302	0.989
52	RGI60-15.06557	3.955	57.084	5.320	0.304
53	RGI60-15.06559	9.906	94.187	11.736	1.105
54	RGI60-15.06807	2.166	39.628	3.884	0.154
55	RGI60-15.06808	2.225	44.018	1.199	0.053
56	RGI60-15.06814	2.173	44.401	1.942	0.086

57	RGI60-15.06815	2.476	50.042	1.819	0.091
58	RGI60-15.06816	2.766	58.993	2.262	0.133
59	RGI60-15.07151	5.540	99.078	2.728	0.270
60	RGI60-15.07168	6.428	107.233	4.346	0.466
61	RGI60-15.08829	3.696	66.468	1.995	0.130

Table S4: Ice thickness and volume of 61 glaciers